

Policy Cloud

Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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D3.6 POLICYCLOUD'S SOCIETAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS & GUIDELINES – M22

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Abstract: This report provides a second version of all the societal and ethical requirements and guidelines as described in Task 3.5. More specifically, this deliverable analyses the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal issues related to PolicyCLOUD and the issues related to each use case. Finally, a review is provided on how the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal requirements are being embedded in the solutions being developed throughout the Project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
API	Application Programming Interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
CCC	Complementary Customer Control
DMA	Data Management Agreement
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
ECI	European Cloud Initiative
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union
EUCS	European Union Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
EULA	End User License Agreement
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
IoT	Internet of Things
ISMS	Information Security Management System
JSA	Jobseekers Allowance
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
LIA	Legitimate Interest Assessment
OGL	Open Government License
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PM	Policy Model
PME	Policy Model Editor
PP	Public Policy
RDWTI	RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism Incidents
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WP	Work Package
UC	Use Case
UX	User Experience
XACML	eXtensible Access Control Markup Language

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Executive Summary

This report provides a second version of all the societal and ethical requirements and guidelines as described in Task 3.5. More specifically, this deliverable analyses the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal issues related to PolicyCLOUD. With regards to ethical and societal issues, from a general standpoint the main findings relate to the importance of ensuring the accuracy of the dataset used for performing the analytics and the policymaking to achieve an adequate degree of reliability on the policies developed based on the same analytics. Also, the respect of the principle of transparency appears relevant to ensure the engagement of the end-users and to obtain their trust in the policies developed through PolicyCLOUD. Moreover, the key issue is to ensure an adequate level of human engagement in the data processing and policymaking processes, to avoid the relevant ethical and societal risks related to a complete automatization of decisional processes, which may be jeopardised by biases (whether in the initial dataset or in the algorithm), leading for example to discrimination phenomena. The general legal and regulatory issues related to the Project concern contractual protection of data sources, legal protection of databases, copyright, and personal data protection and privacy. Of this list, personal data protection is the most important legal and regulatory issue related to the Project since the development of PolicyCLOUD implies the collection and processing of a relevant amount of personal identifiable information. Therefore, compliance with the requirements defined by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable personal data protection regulations is paramount for the correct and sustainable implementation of PolicyCLOUD. Also, by analysing in detail the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal issues related to the components of the Project, the risks appear to be focused on the selection of the datasets to be used, from the perspective of both their accuracy and the legitimacy to collect and process the data for the purposes of the Project. These issues need to be addressed whether the data used constitute personal identifiable information; however, when personal data are involved, appropriate safeguards shall be implemented, especially to comply to applicable data protection laws. Furthermore, this deliverable examines the specific issues related to each of the use cases. Finally, a review is provided on how the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal requirements are being embedded in the solutions being developed throughout the Project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Foreword

The PolicyCLOUD project aims to harness the potential of digitisation, big data, and cloud technologies to improve the modelling, creation, and implementation of policies. In its three-year span (2020-2022), the project will address challenges faced by many businesses and public administrations of improving how they make policy decisions by accessing and using data.

The aim of the PolicyCLOUD project is to deliver a unique, integrated environment of curated datasets and data management, manipulation, and analysis tools – the PolicyCLOUD platform – addressing the full lifecycle of policy management in four distinct thematic areas, and using the data analysis capabilities of the European Cloud Initiative (ECI), with an emphasis on data analysis to facilitate evidence-based policy making. The project introduces a pioneering approach for the development of policies collections to exploit collective knowledge towards policy co-creation and cross-sector optimisation.¹

The members of the PolicyCLOUD project (“**Consortium**”) are aware of the necessity of providing extensive and in-depth analyses of legal, regulatory, societal, and ethical aspects, seeing to an optimal embedding of the results of these into the design of the PolicyCLOUD platform, and thoroughly evaluating the extent to which this has been successful, in order to maximise societal acceptability and trust in the platform and, through this, in policies generated via the platform. Special attention must be paid to the ethical and societal issues which will need attention throughout the project. Therefore, a set of system dimensions, features, and functionalities, and their links to the range of socially and ethically significant new practices that the system enables have been identified, and an initial set of requirements, guidelines and norms for the responsible modelling of policies, aligned with the iterations of the development and demonstration of the Policy CLOUD platform in the relation to the relevant Use Cases (UCs) has been proposed in D3.3 [1].

This Deliverable, which serves as an update to D3.3, will both report on the progress made in the PolicyCLOUD project on the refinement and implementation of the initial set of legal/ethical requirements identified in Section 8.2 of D3.3 [1], and update those requirements with further legal/ethical issues detected during the course of the project (and after submission of D3.3), related to previously and newly defined components, as well as to the different UCs. In particular, the main sections of this Deliverable cover the following points:

- In Section 2 of this Deliverable, refined sets of legal/ethical requirements, initially derived from D3.3 and subsequently consolidated through discussions with the Consortium, are described for

¹ For more information about the Project, see <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870675> and <https://policycloud.eu/>.

each relevant PolicyCLOUD project Work Package (WP), as well as steps taken to implement the resulting requirements as of the date of this Deliverable;

- In [Section 3](#) of this Deliverable, new PolicyCLOUD platform components (not yet designed, or fully designed, as of the date of D3.3) are assessed, and an initial set of legal/ethical requirements is proposed for each component;
- Finally, in [Annex 1 – WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist](#) to [Annex 21 – WP7 Legal/Ethical Checklist](#) to this Deliverable, updated and new lists of legal/ethical requirements are provided, which will be used to track the remaining compliance steps in need of implementation to ensure the legal/ethical soundness of the PolicyCLOUD platform during the final year of the project.²

This Deliverable will be updated one final time (D3.9) in M34 (October 2022).

1.2 Summary of Changes

The objectives of this Deliverable are to provide an update to the initial set of legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements identified in [Section 8.2](#) of D3.3 [1], as well as to report the progress made on the requirements ultimately identified as relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project. It is thus generally focused more on practical considerations than theoretical explanations of relevant legal/ethical issues related to the PolicyCLOUD project, which have already been extensively addressed in [Section 2](#) of D3.3 [1] – readers are generally encouraged to refer to D3.3 for greater detail on the theoretical context surrounding the requirements identified in this Deliverable, as this has not been repeated to avoid redundancy and facilitate legibility of this Deliverable.

² With regards to legal and regulatory issues, the scope of the analysis, in the context of this deliverable, will be generally limited to EU and international law, without exploring in detail the specific national and/or local requirements related to the countries and jurisdictions in which the use cases are implemented. Nevertheless, where specific analysis on local and/or national regulations shall result as appropriate and/or necessary, we will highlight this as a field for which further research is needed and that will be consequently developed in the next version of this deliverable to be released in M34 (October 2022).

2 Specification, Development, and Implementation of Identified Requirements

2.1 Requirements, Architecture & Innovation (WP2)

As noted in [Sections 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5](#) of this Deliverable, based on the key compliance controls indicated in [Section 8.2](#) of D3.3 [1], several consolidated checklists of requirements were developed through multiple discussions with relevant Partners (including, in particular, WP Leaders) – the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, the **WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist** and the **WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists**.

During the discussions around implementation of the requirements reflected in these consolidated checklists, it became apparent that certain requirements – which were identified in multiple (if not all) checklists – could not be addressed in the context of an individual WP, as their implementation would have cross-WP implications, requiring the contribution of several Partners across all WPs. As a result, it is arguably appropriate to address these requirements in the context of WP2, which includes the technical coordination activities for the project within its scope (T2.3).

In the sub-sections below, we will address the 2 cross-WP requirements identified as of the date of this Deliverable.

2.1.1 Data Security

As a cloud-based solution reliant on the analysis of big data (including, potentially, personal data) through the use of various tools – including tools based on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) – the PolicyCLOUD platform is potentially exposed to a number of relevant security threats – affecting the cloud-based infrastructure, the individual platform components and/or the data and analytics tools leveraged via the platform:

- Cloud computing technologies offer an incentive to maximise data collection which, if not properly checked, may create security risks (e.g., related to new types of vulnerabilities created by use of geographically distributed infrastructure and data storage). As an example, the decentralised nature of cloud computing systems increases the exposure of data processed through those systems to interception, loss, alteration, or misuse. It is further important to bear in mind that ensuring the confidentiality and overall security of data processed via cloud-based solutions, as well as mitigating the potential impact of a potential loss of availability affecting the cloud-based system, are core ethical issues in the information ethics context (see [Section 2.1.2](#) of D3.3 [1]);

- The big data ecosystem requires distribution and aggregation of information in modes that were unforeseen in the past. The sophistication and the huge capacity of big data services to process significant volumes of data, automatically and without human intervention, sets critical questions related specifically to security (see [Section 2.1.3](#) of D3.3);
- Design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, and inappropriate or malicious use of platform tools (in particular, AI-based tools) may cause adversarial, critical or damaging effects, leading the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI-HLEG)'s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (referenced and further described in [Section 2.1.4](#) of D3.3) to consider technical robustness and safety as a key ethical consideration for AI-based tools (see [Section 2.1.4](#) of D3.3);
- Breaches of security affecting personal data processed via the platform (i.e., "personal data breaches") may, as highlighted by Recital 85 GDPR, *"if not addressed in an appropriate and timely manner, result in physical, material or non-material damage to natural persons such as loss of control over their personal data or limitation of their rights, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, damage to reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy or any other significant economic or social disadvantage to the natural person concerned"* (see [Section 2.2.4.9](#) of D3.3).

Implementing an appropriate security posture for the PolicyCLOUD platform is not only required to ensure compliance with applicable legal (particularly where personal data may be processed via the platform, as determined by Art. 32 GDPR) and ethical requirements, but also to create trust in PolicyCLOUD users. This, in turn, is necessary to allow such users to justify their choice to rely on PolicyCLOUD towards the individuals for which they are responsible (e.g., citizens under the purview of the policy maker), allowing them to potentially assuage relevant concerns which those individuals may have.

As noted in several of the key compliance controls listed in [Section 8.2](#) of D3.3 [1], in order to ensure that an appropriate security posture, including adequate and effective technical and/or organisational security measures, is implemented for the platform, it is essential to carry out a dedicated platform-wide security risk assessment, through which to identify relevant security threats and identify measures which can feasibly be implemented to mitigate the likelihood and/or impact of each identified threat to an acceptable degree.

In discussions with the Consortium, it was concluded that it is not feasible for each WP to autonomously decide on its approach to the abovementioned security requirements. Such an approach would create an unacceptable risk of inadequacy, inconsistency and incompatibility between the security measures applied to different PolicyCLOUD platform components. It was therefore agreed that PolicyCLOUD project-wide alignment on this matter was essential. As a practical solution to the complexity of coordinating the necessary security risk assessment, and to ensure a reliable/validated approach to this assessment, it was agreed that the European Union Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (EUCS), as a candidate certification scheme focused on the cybersecurity of cloud services,

developed under the European Union (EU) Cybersecurity Act³ by the EU's agency dedicated to achieving a high common level of cybersecurity across Europe, could serve as an appropriate standard by which to measure the security posture of the platform and identify additional technical and/or organisational measures to be implemented. The goal on this would be to implement the EUCS' requirements to the extent they are relevant and feasible to the platform, and to document this appropriately.

The EUCS requirements identified as potentially relevant to the PolicyCLOUD platform, as of the date of this Deliverable, are reported in the new **WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 1 – WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist](#) to this Deliverable. This checklist will be consolidated in further discussions with the Consortium (so as to determine whether any identified requirements are irrelevant or unfeasible, or whether any additional EUCS requirements should be considered), and will subsequently be used to track and document the implementation of the consolidated requirements by the relevant Partners (identified as owners for each requirement in discussions with the Consortium) until the end of the PolicyCLOUD project.

2.1.2 Data Retention

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.8](#) of D3.3 [1], the principle of storage limitation set out under the GDPR requires personal data to be stored for no longer than necessary for the purposes for which it is processed. Even where personal data is lawfully and fairly collected, it cannot be stored for longer than actually needed (unless further retention can be lawfully justified). After this point, stored personal data must either be irreversibly erased or anonymised (e.g., through aggregation). As a result, wherever it is not feasible to avoid collecting personal data in the first place (considering the principle of data minimisation, better described in [Section 2.2.4.6](#) of D3.3), specific retention periods for collected personal data (or rollover/overwrite periods for streaming data), based on the strict minimum period of time for which retention of those data is needed to ensure that the purpose for their collection and processing can be met, must be defined.

There are essentially two types of personal data which may potentially be processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform, and for which – under the GDPR's principle of storage limitation – retention periods need to be defined:

1. Personal data related to PolicyCLOUD users;
2. Personal data contained within data sources processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform.

Concerning the definition of retention periods:

³ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R0881>.

- For 1., the Consortium (or, at least, the Consortium members competent to make decisions as to how such personal data should be handled) are arguably responsible for the definition of retention periods, for the duration of the PolicyCLOUD project. It has been agreed that it is not practically feasible to define a retention period shorter than the duration of the project as of the date of this Deliverable. After the project is completed, this responsibility will arguably be transferred to the organisation(s) ultimately responsible for the management of the PolicyCLOUD platform (“**PolicyCLOUD Manager(s)**”), which may be qualified as controller(s) for such personal data under the GDPR – the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) will then be responsible for revising this retention period, to ensure compliance with the GDPR’s principle of storage limitation.
- For 2., the relevant UC Partner identifying each data source for processing via the PolicyCLOUD platform is arguably responsible for the definition of retention periods applicable to any personal data which is extracted from that data source and further stored on the platform. This is addressed further in [Sections 2.3.5 and 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable.

Concerning the implementation of measures to ensure that, after expiry of a defined retention period, personal data can be irreversibly deleted or anonymised on the platform, this is addressed further in [Sections 2.2.5 and 2.3.5](#) of this Deliverable.

2.2 Cloud Infrastructure Utilization & Data Governance (WP3)

As noted in [Section 3.1.1.1](#) of D3.3 [1], the PolicyCLOUD project will be reliant on a cloud-based infrastructure to provide the necessary computing and storage capabilities to allow the project to fulfil its goals. This infrastructure will be provided by an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) provider, with such provision regulated – as of the date of submission of this deliverable – under the contractual combination of a Service Level Agreement (SLA) entered into between the Consortium and EGI.eu and an Operational Level Agreement (OLA) entered into between EGI.eu and the provider.

Of the key compliance controls indicated in [Section 8.2](#) of D3.3 [1], the following may be considered as relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project’s use of a cloud-based infrastructure:

Area	Type of requirement	Control
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to cloud computing	It is necessary to have a clear and specific framework in place with the IaaS provider, in which objectives, processes and results expected from PolicyCLOUD platform are clearly set out, so as to specify the capabilities needed from the IaaS provider.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to cloud computing	The framework developed with the IaaS provider must define appropriate service levels so as to ensure that the platform and its data will be kept promptly available to PolicyCLOUD and end-users, identifying a maximum amount of acceptable service downtime and ensuring the possibility to recover data which may be lost during the interruption. Infringement of these levels should preferably be subjected to appropriate contractual penalties.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to cloud computing	The environmental impact of the infrastructure necessary to support the functioning of the cloud-based system is reduced to a minimum.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to big data management	The platform should incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated in particular from reliance on big data analysis.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with Data Subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs Data Subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD should implement technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD shall implement technical and organisational measures aimed at guaranteeing the accuracy and quality of personal data included in the cloud-based platform and shall

Area	Type of requirement	Control
		provide means to Data Subjects for contributing to the maintenance of data that is always accurate and up-to-date.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than actually needed, unless a reason for further processing exists, and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle. Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	It should be demonstrable that the security measures implemented on the platform were chosen as a result of a documented risk assessment, with justifications as to why those measures were deemed adequate to address the specific risks identified.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	There should be clearly defined rules and specific channels on the reporting of security incidents or abnormal events related to the platform., and all persons working with the platform should be made aware of the types of occurrences which may qualify as a reportable security incident.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	The processes implemented to address personal data breaches by PolicyCLOUD should ensure that all relevant information on a personal data breach and the manner in which it was handled is documented in a register of personal data breaches, as set out in Art. 33, par. 5 GDPR, including all facts pertaining to the personal data breach, its effects and remedial action taken, including notifications to end-users, supervisory authorities and/or Data Subjects, as well as all technical and organizational mitigation measures applied, documented assessments carried out, including those performed to classify the incident as a personal data breach, as well as to classify a

Area	Type of requirement	Control
		personal data breach in terms of category and severity level. Post-breach analyses should also be carried out, to validate the effectiveness of the breach management process, identify areas of improvement, and identify, based on a root cause analysis of the incident, adequate technical and organisational measures to reduce or eliminate the likelihood of recurrence.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	A security risk assessment, as part of an overall Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), should be carried out, to identify possible threats and risks to the fundamental rights, freedoms and interests of Data Subjects and the specific security measures implemented or which should be implemented to address them.
Legal/Regulatory	Requirements related to the use of the Cloud Infrastructure	A Data Processing Agreement (DPA) shall be executed between PolicyCLOUD and the IaaS provider, including all the requirements defined by Art. 28 GDPR.
Ethical / Legal / Regulatory / Societal	Requirements related to the use of the Cloud Infrastructure	PolicyCLOUD shall perform a comprehensive risk assessment, focused on the likelihood and impact of threats to confidentiality, integrity and/or availability of assets stored on the platform, and to the resilience of the infrastructure of the platform and systems itself, as well as relevant compliance obstacles raised by use of the cloud infrastructure, and assess whether the technical and organisational measures put in place by the IaaS provider in relation to the cloud infrastructure sufficiently mitigate any relevant risks identified.

TABLE 1 – WP3 KEY COMPLIANCE CONTROLS (D3.3)

Following the submission of D3.3, through multiple discussions with the relevant Partners (including, in particular, the WP3 Leader), the above requirements were consolidated and incorporated into the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**. This resulted in the current list of applicable requirements relevant to the project’s cloud-based infrastructure:

Control No.	Recommendation
1	It is necessary to have a clear and specific framework in place with the IaaS provider, in which objectives, processes and results expected from PolicyCLOUD platform are clearly set out, so as to specify the capabilities needed from the IaaS provider.
2	The framework developed with the IaaS provider must define appropriate service levels so as to ensure that the platform and its data will be kept promptly available to PolicyCLOUD and end-users, identifying a maximum amount of acceptable service

Control No.	Recommendation
	<p>downtime and ensuring the possibility to recover data which may be lost during the interruption.</p> <p>Infringement of these levels should preferably be subjected to appropriate contractual penalties.</p>
3	<p>The environmental impact of the infrastructure necessary to support the functioning of the cloud-based system should be reduced to a minimum.</p>
4	<p>Adequate technical and organisational security measures must be implemented in the components developed by WP3, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis.</p> <p>Specific measures aimed at ensuring data integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data used as input, the functioning of the analytics components, or the output generated by those components) should be considered in this assessment, as well as specific measures aimed at ensuring data confidentiality/availability (where input datasets may be stored on the platform), and restrictions on reuse of personal data (e.g., hashing or encryption).</p> <p>The ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents, including personal data breaches, must also be considered.</p> <p>The technical and organisational security measures put in place by the IaaS provider in relation to the cloud infrastructure should sufficiently mitigate any relevant risks identified.</p>
5	<p>The Platform should be designed so as to facilitate the exercise of rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws to the relevant data subjects (i.e., platform users).</p> <p>This may include measures such as setting up a dedicated e-mail inbox to receive requests for the exercise of these rights, as well as an internal workflow which allows for adequate management of these requests within the timeframe provided by the GDPR (as a rule, requests must be addressed within one month from receipt).</p> <p>Furthermore, the Platform should be designed so as to not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights.</p>
6	<p>Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.</p>
7	<p>PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data (of platform users) in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.</p> <p>Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than actually needed, unless a reason for further processing exists,</p>

Control No.	Recommendation
	and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle. Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.
8	A DPA shall be executed between PolicyCLOUD and the IaaS provider, including all the requirements defined by Art. 28 GDPR.

TABLE 2 – WP3 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

We will now cover the steps taken to address each of these controls, as of the date of this Deliverable.

2.2.1 IaaS Provider Framework

Under Controls no. 1, 2 and 8 of the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to define and implement a clear and specific framework with the provider for the PolicyCLOUD project's cloud-based infrastructure. This framework should:

- Clearly set out the project's expectations from the infrastructure in terms of objectives, processes and results;
- Specify the capabilities needed from the infrastructure/provider in order to allow those expectations to be met;
- Define appropriate service levels so as to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform and its data are kept promptly available throughout the project and towards end-users;
- Ensure that, where any personal data are hosted on this infrastructure in connection with the project, the provider is bound by appropriate obligations regarding those personal data towards the Consortium, under the GDPR.

To meet these requirements, as reported in Section 3.1.1.1 of D3.3 [1], an SLA was entered into between the Consortium and the relevant Partner (EGI.eu) [26], and an OLA was entered into between EGI.eu and the provider [27]. Both documents were finalised on 13 October 2020. Together, these documents combine to lay down several important stipulations pertaining to the provision of cloud-based infrastructure services relevant to the project:

- The services provided are clearly defined (see Section 1 of the SLA and OLA);
- The service hours, and relevant exceptions to the defined hours, are clearly defined (see Section 2 of the SLA and OLA);
- Response times concerning relevant security incidents and service requests are clearly defined (see Section 3 of the SLA and OLA);

- Service level targets, in terms of monthly service availability⁴, monthly service reliability⁵ and quality of support level, are clearly defined (see [Section 4](#) of the SLA and OLA);
- Service limitations and constraints (e.g., language used for technical support services, downtime resulting from critical security upgrades) are established (see [Section 5](#) of the SLA and OLA);
- The responsibilities of the provider/EGL.eu (e.g., monitoring/limiting resource usage appropriately, notifying resource termination in advance, ensuring sufficient resources/connectivity to support proper service operation, adherence to relevant policies/procedures, monitoring of service levels) are clearly defined (see [Section 8](#) of the SLA and OLA).

As subsequently reported in D3.4 [28], EGL.eu has been monitoring the performance of the provider since the execution of the OLA and SLA, in order to make sure that the resources and the services requested by the Consortium are being delivered according to the service targets described in these agreements. This is carried out via a specific dashboard in ARGO: a lightweight service for service level monitoring designed for medium and large-sized research infrastructures.

As of the date of D3.4, EGL.eu has produced a first service performance report showing the monthly availability and the monthly reliability of the provider's services from August 2020 to January 2021. EGL.eu has further conducted satisfaction reviews with the relevant Partners on a regular basis, in order to collect feedback about the status of the agreements, identify suggestions for improvement and additional requests to scale-up the initial resources allocated by the provider.

As specified in D3.3 [1], where the provision of this infrastructure may involve the processing of personal data on behalf of the Consortium (i.e., where personal data may be hosted, in connection with the PolicyCLOUD project, on this infrastructure), the provider is arguably acting as a processor on behalf of the Consortium. This is because, in providing the services, the provider merely offers the Consortium the ability to host such personal data on its infrastructure, without actively processing those personal data itself for any of its own purposes – it is thus reasonable to maintain that the provider merely acts as a processor, under Art. 4(8) GDPR, on behalf of the Consortium. Given that the contractual framework in place is that the Consortium has entered into an agreement with EGL.eu (SLA), and EGL.eu has “subcontracted” the services agreed with the Consortium to the provider (via the OLA), it is reasonable to qualify EGL.eu more specifically as acting as a processor, regarding such personal data, on behalf of the Consortium⁶, and the provider as acting as a “sub-processor” on behalf of EGL.eu.

⁴ Defined as “*the ability of a service to fulfil its intended function at a specific time or over a calendar month*”.

⁵ Defined as “*the ability of a service to fulfil its intended function at a specific time or over a calendar month, excluding scheduled maintenance periods*”.

⁶ Note that this does not imply that the Consortium necessarily acts as a controller for these personal data. As seen, e.g., in [Section 2.4.2](#) of this Deliverable, the data processing role played by the Consortium

Art. 28(3) GDPR requires any processing of personal data carried out by a processor (or sub-processor) to be governed by “*a contract or other legal act under Union or Member State law, that is binding on the processor with regard to the controller and that sets out the subject-matter and duration of the processing, the nature and purpose of the processing, the type of personal data and categories of data subjects and the obligations and rights of the controller*”. This is typically referred to as a data processing agreement, or “**DPA**”. Art. 28(3) GDPR goes on to establish a set of minimum obligations which must be included in such a data processing agreement, as identified in [Section 3.1.1.1](#) of D3.3 [1].

To meet these requirements, EGI.eu has since made template data processing agreements available, which may be used to complement the OLA and SLA with additional obligations upon EGI.eu/the provider. In particular, the template DPA with EGI Foundation as a Processor relevant to Cloud Compute services [29] may, subject to a full assessment and consolidation of its contents to ensure its adequacy in light of the personal data processing activities relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project, be leveraged for these purposes.

The status of implementation of the requirements concerning the framework in place with the IaaS provider, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.2.2 Environmental Impact

Under [Control no. 3](#) of the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to define and implement technical and/or organisational measures to ensure that the environmental impact of the PolicyCLOUD project’s cloud-based infrastructure is reduced to a minimum. As noted in D3.3 [1], from a societal perspective, it is important to consider the potential impact on environmental sustainability which leveraging a cloud-based infrastructure may have, as opposed to relying on local infrastructure and/or storage capabilities (e.g., will this lead to less emissions and energy consumption given the reliance on shared resources, or will those shared resources produce even more emissions?). The Consortium should ensure that reliance on cloud-based infrastructure is not only more technically efficient than non-cloud-based alternatives, but also that the environmental impact of this choice is reduced to a minimum (to avoid having the benefits of this choice being lessened or even ultimately outweighed by this impact over time).

While a relevant owner for the implementation of this Control has been identified (with the note that the provider should also be involved in this discussion), there are no further practical steps to report, as of the date of this Deliverable, towards the implementation of this Control.

(or by specific Partners within the Consortium) will vary according to the type of data subjects at hand (e.g., PolicyCLOUD users, individuals whose personal data is included in datasets processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform).

The status of implementation of the requirements concerning the environmental impact of the PolicyCLOUD project's environmental infrastructure, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the updated **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.2.3 Data Security

Under [Controls no. 4 and 6](#) of the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to define and implement adequate technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of data hosted on the PolicyCLOUD project's cloud-based infrastructure. These measures should be defined as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis (but also from use of a cloud-based infrastructure, in general). Specific goals to be met by such measures include:

- Ensuring integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data, analytics tools or the output of those tools which may be hosted on the cloud-based infrastructure);
- Ensuring confidentiality (e.g., prevention of unauthorised access to, or disclosure of, data, analytics tools or the output of those tools which may be hosted on the cloud-based infrastructure);
- Ensuring availability (e.g., prevention of loss of the ability to promptly access and make legitimate use of data, analytics tools or the output of those tools which may be hosted on the cloud-based infrastructure);
- Restricting unlawful reuse of personal data hosted on the cloud-based infrastructure (e.g., appropriate access controls, relevant technical and contractual limitations on such reuse);
- Ensuring the ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents affecting the cloud-based infrastructure.

Data security concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to its cloud-based infrastructure – are more generally covered in [Section 2.1.1](#) of this Deliverable.

In particular, as specified in [Section 3.1.1.2](#) of D.3.3 [1], it is recommended that the dedicated security risk assessment concerning the provider's cloud-based infrastructure be guided by existing standards, as these may provide credible and authoritative support in determining whether the security measures applied to this infrastructure may be deemed adequate. It will thus be important for PolicyCLOUD to determine what standard (or standards) to rely on. To this end, examples which PolicyCLOUD may wish to consider include the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)'s (draft) EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme [30], ENISA's Information Assurance Framework [31], Cloud Security Alliance's Cloud Controls Matrix [32] and relevant ISO/IEC standards.⁷

⁷ Including ISO/IEC 27001:2013, ISO/IEC 27002, and ISO/IEC 27017:2015.

Regarding the implementation of specific restrictions on the unlawful reuse of personal data, as reported in [Section 6.3](#) of D3.4 [28], a Data Governance and Privacy Enforcement mechanism has been developed for the PolicyCLOUD platform, which includes three different parts:

- An access policy editor, which provides the ability to define and store access policies based on the Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) scheme, according to the eXtensible Access Control Markup Language (XACML) standard;
- A model and model editor, which is used to define these policies and enforce them; and
- An ABAC authorisation engine, which is used to evaluate policies and attributes, thus enforcing protection and privacy-preserving policies.

Through this mechanism, as initially reported in [Section 5.2.1](#) of D3.1 [1], it is possible to determine whether or not a user of the PolicyCLOUD platform is able to access a given piece of data, file, database, folder or other “object” hosted on the platform’s cloud-based infrastructure based on at least 5 contextual attributes:

- The type of “object” to be accessed;
- The user (or software) requesting access;
- The location of the requester;
- The date and time of the request;
- The type of device and connection used to make the request, as well as details on connection security and metrics.

In connection with the above, as reported in [Section 6.4](#) (and, in particular, [Section 6.4.2](#)) of D3.4 [28], the PolicyCLOUD platform has been crafted in such a manner as to support various different data governance models.

To complement these technical access controls, contractual limitations on individuals’ ability to process personal data collected and managed via the PolicyCLOUD platform should be put in place. This means that PolicyCLOUD users, as well as personnel of the IaaS provider and the Consortium with access to personal data, should be restricted (through enforceable contractual obligations) from making undue use of personal data to which they may have access in connection with the PolicyCLOUD platform or project. This can be addressed as follows:

- **PolicyCLOUD users:** Please refer to [Section 2.4.1](#) of this Deliverable.
- **IaaS provider personnel:** Under Art. 28(3)(b) and 29 GDPR, processors (such as the provider) are required to ensure that the persons which they authorise to process personal data are bound by appropriate confidentiality obligations, and do not process those data except on instructions from the relevant controller (which may be given to them by the processor, on the controller’s behalf). To this end, the template data processing agreements made available by EGI.eu must be fully assessed and consolidated to ensure that these requirements are met, after which they should be executed between the Consortium and EGI.eu (in connection with the SLA), and between EGI.eu and the provider (in connection with the OLA), respectively.

- **Consortium personnel:** Each Consortium member (other than EGI.eu, which will be covered by the consolidated data processing agreement mentioned above), regardless of whether they act as a controller or a processor for the personal data which may be processed in connection with the PolicyCLOUD project, is solely responsible for ensuring that all personnel they involve in the PolicyCLOUD project is bound by appropriate confidentiality obligations, as well as by an obligation not to process any such data except on instructions from the relevant Consortium member.

The status of implementation of general data security requirements concerning the PolicyCLOUD project, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 1](#) – WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

The status of implementation of specific requirements concerning the implementation of restrictions on the unlawful reuse of personal data, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.2.4 Data Subject Rights

Under [Controls no. 5 and 7](#) of the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to ensure that the cloud infrastructure on which the PolicyCLOUD platform is hosted allows for the exercise of rights granted by the GDPR, or by other applicable laws, to individuals whose personal data may be processed via the platform (i.e., “**Data Subject Rights**”) – at a minimum, this infrastructure should not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights. As reported in [Sections 2.2.4.3 and 2.2.4.7](#) of D3.3 [1], the GDPR’s principle of fairness requires the Consortium to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform is designed and implemented in such a manner that it is capable of facilitating the exercise of these rights (by having effective mechanisms in place to allow for this), and the GDPR’s principle of accuracy specifies this by affording those individuals the general right to an overview of, and easy access to, their personal data which is processed via the platform, to allow them to control its accuracy and rectify it as needed. This requires the Consortium to ensure that the platform allows the querying of any such data to identify, extract, modify and/or delete personal data pertaining to an individual. As noted also in [Section 2.2.4.8](#) of D3.3, the GDPR’s principle of storage limitation also requires the Consortium to ensure that there are effective and irreversible functionalities for the deletion and/or anonymisation of any personal data stored on the platform (which should preferably be automated) – such functionalities would also allow the platform to facilitate the exercise of specific Data Subject Rights, such as the right to erasure (under Arts. 17 and 19 GDPR), the right to object (under Art. 21 GDPR) and the right to withdrawal of consent (under Art. 7(3) GDPR).

To assist the Consortium in meeting these requirements concerning users of the PolicyCLOUD platform, the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** was expanded to include a description of the rights afforded to individuals under the GDPR, and an indication of the technical abilities which the PolicyCLOUD platform

should allow (either under individuals' autonomous control, or under the control of platform system administrators) to ensure that these rights can be appropriately exercised:

	Description	Abilities Needed
<p>Right of Access Art. 15 GDPR</p>	<p>(1) Data subjects have the right to obtain confirmation as to whether or not personal data concerning them are being processed.</p>	<p>The ability to confirm if personal data on a given individual is contained within the platform's databases, through relevant identifiers.</p>
	<p>(2) If (1) applies, data subjects have the right to obtain access to those personal data.</p>	<p>The ability to either provide a given individual with direct access to the personal data held on them (e.g., through a registered account on a platform), or to provide individuals with a dataset containing their personal data by other means - this ties in to (4).</p>
	<p>(3) If (1) applies, data subjects have the right to obtain information on how those personal data are being processed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The purposes for which those personal data are processed; - The categories of personal data concerned; - The recipients (or categories of recipients) to whom their personal data has been, or will be disclosed; - The envisaged retention period(s) for their personal data, or at least the criteria used to determine such retention period(s); - Their rights under the GDPR, and how they can be exercised; - Any information available as to the source(s) from which their personal data was collected (if they were not provided directly by the data subject); - Whether any "automated individual decisions" (i.e., decisions taken solely by automated means, such as by an algorithm) are taken regarding them and, if this is the case, information about the logic involved in these decisions, their significance and potential consequences for the data subject; - The safeguards put in place to ensure the lawfulness of transfers of personal data to a third country (non-EEA), if applicable. 	<p>The ability to identify and provide all of this information regarding the personal data handled on the relevant data subjects.</p>

	Description	Abilities Needed
	(4) If (1) applies, data subjects have the right to obtain a copy of those personal data.	The ability to extract all personal data related to a given individual which is stored and share this dataset with the individual (in any relevant, legible format).
Right to Rectification Art. 16 GDPR Art. 19 GDPR	(1) Data subjects have the right to obtain, without undue delay, the rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning them.	<p>The ability to edit specific data points stored on a given individual within the platform's databases.</p> <p>Ideally, the individual should have the ability to edit their own personal data autonomously (e.g., through a registered account on a platform).</p>
	(2) Data subjects have the right to have incomplete personal data completed, including by means of providing a supplementary statement.	The ability to add information to data stored on a given individual within the platform's databases.
	(3) Data subjects have the right to have their rectification requests communicated to each recipient to whom their personal data has been disclosed, unless this is impossible or involves a disproportionate amount of effort.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to relay a rectification request to those recipients.
	(4) Data subjects have the right to have the recipients to whom their personal data has been disclosed identified, upon request.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to communicate this information to that individual.
Right to Erasure Art. 17 GDPR Art. 19 GDPR	(1) Data subjects have the right, under certain circumstances, to obtain the erasure of personal data concerning them without undue delay.	<p>The ability to delete data (specific data points, or all data points) stored on a given individual within the platform's databases.</p> <p>Ideally, the individual should have the ability to trigger this process autonomously (e.g., by selecting an option to terminate their registered account on a platform, or by clicking on an unsubscribe link in a marketing communication received).</p>
	(2) Where personal data on a given data subject has been made public, the data subject has the right to require the controller which made those personal data public to take reasonable steps, including technical measures, to inform others which are processing those personal data that	The ability to notify others of requests for erasure received, regarding personal data which has been made public.

	Description	Abilities Needed
	the data subject has requested the erasure of links to those personal data, as well as any copies or replications of those personal data.	
	(3) Data subjects have the right to have their erasure requests communicated to each recipient to whom their personal data has been disclosed, unless this is impossible or involves a disproportionate amount of effort.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to relay a erasure request to those recipients.
	(4) Data subjects have the right to have the recipients to whom their personal data has been disclosed identified, upon request.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to communicate this information to that individual.
Right to Restriction of Processing Art. 18 GDPR Art. 19 GDPR	(1) Data subjects have the right, under certain circumstances, to obtain the temporary restriction of the processing of their personal data. Restricted personal data may continue to be stored (i.e., it does not have to be deleted), but it can only be further processed if the data subject consents, if this is necessary to deal with legal claims, if this is necessary to protect the rights of another individual or legal person, or if this is necessary for reasons of important public interest of the Union or a Member-State.	The ability to mark specific data points stored on a given individual within the platform's databases for a determined period of time, so that those data points are not further processed normally while that mark remains active. In particular, this should be ensured by technical means in such a manner that marked data are not subject to further processing operations and cannot be changed. Marked data should be clearly indicated as restricted within a platform's processing systems.
	(2) Data subjects whose personal data have been temporarily restricted have the right to be informed before the restriction is lifted.	The ability to reach out to the data subject when the determined period of time for restriction is close to expiring.
	(3) Data subjects have the right to have their restriction requests communicated to each recipient to whom their personal data has been disclosed, unless this is impossible or involves a disproportionate amount of effort.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to relay a restriction request to those recipients.
	(4) Data subjects have the right to have the recipients to whom their personal data has been disclosed identified, upon request.	The ability to identify the recipients of personal data on a given individual, and to communicate this information to that individual.
Right to Data Portability Art. 20 GDPR	(1) Data subjects have the right to receive personal data which they have provided in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format.	The ability to extract the personal data related to a given individual which is stored and which was provided directly by that individual,

	Description	Abilities Needed
		and to share this dataset with the individual (in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format, just as .XML, .JSON, .CSV...).
	(2) Data subjects have the right to transmit the personal data provided to them to others, without hindrance from the controller.	The ability to ensure that a given individual, after their personal data has been provided to them in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format, will not suffer relevant technical obstacles created by the controller if they decide to share those personal data with others (such as the controller's competitors).
	(3) Where technically feasible, data subjects have the right to have a controller transmit their personal data directly to another.	The ability to directly transmit the personal data of one individual to another organisation, so that it can be readily used by that other organisation (where feasible).
Right to Object Art. 21 GDPR	(1) Data subjects have the right to object to the processing of their personal data for a given purpose, based on grounds relating to their particular situation.	The ability to mark specific data points stored on a given individual within the platform's databases for a determined period of time, so that those data points can no longer be further processed for a given purpose. If there are no further purposes for which those data can lawfully be used (because the data were only collected for one purpose, or because the other purposes have also been objected to), the ability to delete those data within the platform's databases.
Right to Withdrawal of Consent Art. 7(3) GDPR	(1) If a data subject has provided their consent to the processing of their personal data for a specific purpose, they have the right to withdraw that consent at any time.	The ability to mark specific data points stored on a given individual within the platform's databases for a determined period of time, so that those data points can no longer be further processed for a given purpose. If there are no further purposes for which those data can lawfully be used (because the data were only collected for one purpose, or because the other purposes have also been objected to), the ability to

	Description	Abilities Needed
		delete those data within the platform's databases.

TABLE 3 – WP3 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST: DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS

The status of implementation of specific requirements concerning the implementation of measures to ensure the exercise of Data Subject Rights, concerning PolicyCLOUD users, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable. In particular, it has been confirmed that the abilities described above can be covered via the PolicyCLOUD platform, at least through manual intervention by system administrators. It thus appears, as of the date of this Deliverable, that the cloud-based infrastructure on which the PolicyCLOUD platform is hosted does not present any relevant technical obstacles to the implementation of these abilities and, consequently, to the exercise of data subject rights, concerning PolicyCLOUD users.

The implementation of these requirements concerning other relevant individuals (e.g., individuals whose personal data may be contained in data sources processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform) is addressed in [Section 2.3.4](#) of this Deliverable.

2.2.5 Data Retention

Under [Control no. 7](#) of the **WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to ensure that personal data is not stored on the PolicyCLOUD platform for any longer than necessary to allow the purposes for its lawful collection/further processing to be met. In other words, specific retention periods for such personal data, defined considering the purposes for which such data are used, should be implemented in the PolicyCLOUD project and on the platform – where a retention period is exceeded, the personal data to which it relates should be erased or, alternatively, anonymised (e.g., via aggregation), unless a legal basis can be identified, under the GDPR, for its further retention.

Data retention concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to its cloud-based infrastructure – are more generally covered in [Section 2.1.2](#) of this Deliverable.

In order to ensure that, concerning personal data related to PolicyCLOUD users, after a defined retention period is exceeded, such personal data can be effectively erased or anonymised, the ability to erase or anonymise such personal data (either automatically, or manually) must be implemented.

The status of implementation of specific requirements concerning the implementation of measures to ensure the ability to erase or anonymise personal data, concerning PolicyCLOUD users, after the exceeding of a defined retention period, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable. In particular, it has been confirmed that a mechanism for deletion of such personal data will be implemented within the PolicyCLOUD platform. It thus appears, as of the date of this Deliverable, that the cloud-based infrastructure on which the platform is hosted does not present any relevant technical obstacles to the

implementation of this ability and, consequently, to the possibility to enforce defined retention periods for such personal data.

The implementation of this ability concerning stored personal data related to other relevant individuals (e.g., individuals whose personal data may be contained in datasets processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform) is addressed in Section 2.3.5 of this Deliverable.

2.3 Reusable Models & Analytical Tools (WP4)

As noted in Sections 3.1.3, 3.1.4 and 3.2 of D3.3 [1], the PolicyCLOUD platform will leverage technical components capable of performing operations on data (whether this is personal data or not) extracted from a data source which is selected for processing via the platform, in order to meet multiple objectives, such as:

- The transformation and “pre-processing” of data (as better described in Sections 3.2.1.2 and 3.2.2 of D4.3 [33]), including activities such as:
 - Data validation, to ensure that the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform components operates on clean, correct and useful data. This also involves assessing the data against defined constraints (which may be mandatory or optional), as a way to provide further assurances as to the accuracy and consistency of data processed via the platform;
 - Data cleaning, to correct or remove all data for which validation errors were raised during the validation process, including missing, irregular, unnecessary and inconsistent data. This also involves deleting or replacing data which is not aligned with the defined constraints;
 - Data verification, to check the data for accuracy and any remaining inconsistencies, after the validation and cleaning processes have been completed.
- The enhancement of the semantic and syntactic interoperability of transformed / “pre-processed” data (as better described in Sections 3.2.1.1 and 3.2.3 of D4.3), in order to deliver a structured output which can be used and queried in a more flexible and extendable manner by the PolicyCLOUD platform and its users, including activities such as:
 - Identifying relevant, publicly available and widely used classifications and vocabularies which can be used to codify and assign dimensions, attributes and measures to transformed / “pre-processed” data;
 - Further processing of transformed / “pre-processed” data with the support of the identified classifications and vocabularies, by leveraging different technologies, such as:
 - Linked data and semantic web technologies, in order to link structured data, received from different data sources;
 - Natural language processing technologies, to enhance the analysis and processing of data in the form of raw documents/text (e.g., social media posts, reports) or other forms of unstructured data;
 - Semantic artificial intelligence technologies, to apply machine learning algorithms to sets of structured and unstructured data from various data sources, allowing

such data to be correlated and integrated in a manner which goes beyond the capabilities of traditional, relational tools.

- The application of different analytical tools to this structured output (as better described in [Section 4](#) of D4.3), including tools such as:
 - Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis, which aims at leveraging machine learning techniques to derive high-level descriptions from real world situations, through activities such as exploratory analysis, data source categorisation and predictive analysis;
 - Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis, which is focused on the analysis of text data, and aims, *inter alia*, at extracting sentiments/opinions and other meaningful information from text, categorising text based on PolicyCLOUD user-defined keywords, and allowing the analysis of relevant trends detected in the analysed data;
 - Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics, which focuses on providing PolicyCLOUD users with the means to simulate the potential impact of policy decisions, by estimating the social effects of such decisions and producing flexible simulation models based on user input.

Additionally, as noted in [Sections 2.1.2, 2.2.2 and 2.2.3](#) of D4.3 [33], the PolicyCLOUD platform is designed to allow for the registration of additional analytics tools (usable in the transformation / “pre-processing”, interoperability enhancement and/or structured output analysis phases described above), as well as for the registration of data sources on which such tools (whether pre-existing on the platform, or subsequently registered) can be applied. A set of parameters must be met for the successful registration of tools or data sources, after which they can be made available for use by authorised PolicyCLOUD users.

Of the key compliance controls indicated in [Section 8.2](#) of D3.3 [1], the following may be considered as relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project’s use of a cloud-based infrastructure:

Area	Type of Control requirement	Control
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to big data management	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to big data management	The platform should incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated in particular from reliance on big data analysis.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to AI	Mechanisms facilitating the auditability of AI systems (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data, and the logging of the AI system processes, outcomes, and positive and negative impacts) should be put in place.
Ethical/Societal	Ethical and societal requirements related to AI	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.

Area	Type of requirement	Control
Legal/Regulatory	Contractual protection of data sources	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the data source owner.
Legal/Regulatory	Legal protection of databases	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the rights holder.
Legal/Regulatory	Protection of copyright	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the rights holder.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	When Data Subjects seek to exercise their rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws PolicyCLOUD shall be capable to facilitate the exercise of these rights.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	Internal policies shall be implemented to make users aware of what they can and cannot do with the personal data collected for the different use cases and more in general for the execution of the Project.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD should implement technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD shall only collect personal data, which is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. As such, for each purpose of processing connected to the Project, it shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal data protection and privacy	PolicyCLOUD shall implement technical and organisational measures aimed at guaranteeing the accuracy and quality of personal data included in the cloud-based platform and shall

Area	Type of requirement	Control
		provide means to Data Subjects for contributing to the maintenance of data that is always accurate and up-to-date.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal protection and privacy	data and
		PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than actually needed, unless a reason for further processing exists, and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle. Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal protection and privacy	data and
		It should be demonstrable that the security measures implemented on the platform were chosen as a result of a documented risk assessment, with justifications as to why those measures were deemed adequate to address the specific risks identified.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal protection and privacy	data and
		There should be clearly defined rules and specific channels on the reporting of security incidents or abnormal events related to the platform., and all persons working with the platform should be made aware of the types of occurrences which may qualify as a reportable security incident.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal protection and privacy	data and
		The processes implemented to address personal data breaches by PolicyCLOUD should ensure that all relevant information on a personal data breach and the manner in which it was handled is documented in a register of personal data breaches, as set out in Art. 33, par. 5 GDPR, including all facts pertaining to the personal data breach, its effects and remedial action taken, including notifications to end-users, supervisory authorities and/or Data Subjects, as well as all technical and organizational mitigation measures applied, documented assessments carried out, including those performed to classify the incident as a personal data breach, as well as to classify a personal data breach in terms of category and severity level. Post-breach analyses should also be carried out, to validate the effectiveness of the breach management process, identify areas of improvement, and identify, based on a root cause analysis of the incident, adequate technical and organisational measures to reduce or eliminate the likelihood of recurrence.
Legal/Regulatory	Personal protection and privacy	data and
		A security risk assessment, as part of an overall DPIA, should be carried out, to identify possible threats and risks to the fundamental rights, freedoms and interests of Data Subjects

Area	Type of requirement	Control
		and the specific security measures implemented or which should be implemented to address them.
Ethical / Legal / Regulatory / Societal	Requirements related to the use of the Enhanced Interoperability component	Regarding the Enhanced Interoperability component, PolicyCLOUD should ensure that enough testing is performed to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for annotations and connections established. This may require an extensive training exercise involving various kinds of data sources, to refine rules used by this component for these activities.
Ethical / Legal / Regulatory / Societal	Requirements related to the use of the Enhanced Interoperability component	The Enhanced Interoperability component shall methodically log the activities performed to ensure traceability and presents correlations established and their rationale to the end-user for confirmation, to provide some level of human validation of those correlations. End-users should also be advised of the possibility of false positive correlations, so that they are incentivised to verify the validity of correlations made.
Ethical / Legal / Regulatory / Societal	Requirements related to data analytics	PolicyCLOUD should ensure that enough testing is performed to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for the analytics functions. Any operations performed on data should be methodically logged to ensure traceability, and the general rationale and logic behind the analytics performed should be explained to end-users, so this can be considered during their decision-making process. End-users should be advised of the possibility of false positives or false negatives and errors in result presentation, so that they are incentivised to critically examine results produced by the analytics functions in their decision-making process.

TABLE 4 – WP4 KEY COMPLIANCE CONTROLS (D3.3)

Following the submission of D3.3, through multiple discussions with the relevant Partners (including, in particular, the WP4 Leader), the above requirements were consolidated and incorporated into the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**. This resulted in the current list of applicable requirements relevant to the project’s cloud-based infrastructure:

Control No.	Recommendation
1	<p>The platform's analytic components (including analytic-ingest components) must be covered by an appropriate initial and routine training and testing protocol/program.</p> <p>This protocol/program must aim to mitigate the risk that the components may skew knowledge obtained from data (output) in a biased or otherwise erroneous manner. It must also aim to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for output generated (e.g., in the case of Enhanced Interoperability, for annotations and connections established).</p>

Control No.	Recommendation
2	<p>Adequate technical and organisational security measures must be implemented in the components developed by WP4, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis.</p> <p>Specific measures aimed at ensuring data integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data used as input, the functioning of the analytics components, or the output generated by those components) should be considered in this assessment, as well as specific measures aimed at ensuring data confidentiality/availability (where input datasets may be stored on the platform), and restrictions on reuse of personal data (e.g., hashing or encryption).</p> <p>The ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents, including personal data breaches, must also be considered.</p>
3	<p>Mechanisms facilitating the auditability of AI systems (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data, and the logging of the AI system processes, outcomes, and positive and negative impacts) must be implemented.</p> <p>These logs should assist in ensuring traceability of automated decisions (i.e., explaining how an algorithm arrived at a given output from a given input), as well as the presentation of correlations established and their rationale to the end-user for confirmation. This information should allow end-users to validate correlations made to some extent.</p>
4	<p>Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.</p>
5	<p>Should the use of a selected data source be subject to restrictions (e.g., contractual terms, database copyright protection, database sui generis right protection, copyright protection), that data source should not be used without appropriate permissions from the relevant owners/rightsholders of that data source.</p>
6	<p>The Platform should be designed so as to facilitate the exercise of rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws to the relevant data subjects (i.e., individuals whose personal data may be stored within cleaned/ingested datasets).</p> <p>This may include measures such as setting up a dedicated e-mail inbox to receive requests for the exercise of these rights, as well as an internal workflow which allows for adequate management of these requests within the timeframe provided by the GDPR (as a rule, requests must be addressed within one month from receipt).</p> <p>Furthermore, the Platform should be designed so as to not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights. In particular, regarding personal data stored within cleaned/ingested datasets, it should be possible to manipulate those personal data as needed to respond to any of the requests described in the "Data Subject Rights" tab.</p>
7	<p>Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.</p>

Control No.	Recommendation
8	PolicyCLOUD shall only collect personal data, which is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. As such, for each purpose of processing connected to the Project, it shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.
9	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, and to maintain those personal data up to date over time.
10	End-users should also be advised of the possibility of false positive/negative correlations, so that they are incentivised to verify the validity of correlations made.

TABLE 5 – WP4 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

We will now cover the steps taken to address each of these controls, as of the date of this Deliverable.

2.3.1 Analytics Compliance (including Analytics Tool Registration)

Under Controls no. 1, 3, 4 and 10 of the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to ensure that the activities involving pre-existing analytics tools incorporated into the PolicyCLOUD platform – notably, the tools which are to be implemented in order to carry out activities in the transformation / “pre-processing”, interoperability enhancement and/or structured output analysis phases (as described above, and better described in D4.3 [33]) – are aligned with applicable legal and ethical requirements. This is important both to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform is lawfully usable (at least, under the EU legal framework), and that the trustworthiness of the PolicyCLOUD platform is maximised (which helps to ensure greater user adherence to the platform and societal acceptability of policies created using platform output).

To this end, it is important to implement technical and/or organisational measures to ensure that the following risks are reasonably and substantially minimised (as noted in Section 3.2.1 of D3.3 [1]):

- Output generated by these activities leading to skewed, biased, inaccurate or otherwise misleading information being derived from a given data source, which may potentially culminate in misguided policy-making activities;
- Opacity in the output generation process, such that the ability to explain/understand how a given output was generated by these activities from a given input (as well as the possibility of false positives/negatives or other errors) is reduced or non-existent, which may potentially prevent or disincentivise PolicyCLOUD users from critically examining the output / information derived from a given data source during their decision-making process.

As AI-based technologies (including machine learning) are leveraged in connection with some of these tools, adherence to the 7 key requirements described in the AI-HLEG’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI [35] (further described in Section 2.1.4 of D3.3 [1]) is also recommended as an important step towards maximising the trustworthiness of the PolicyCLOUD platform.

As described in Sections 2.1.2 and 2.2.3 of D4.3 [33], the PolicyCLOUD platform has been designed not only to include pre-existing analytics tools, but also to allow for additional analytics tools to be registered for use via the platform. Additional tools which are registered should also be held to a high standard of

legal/ethical compliance, as noted in [Section 2.3.3](#) of D4.3 [33]. This is important, *inter alia*, to ensure that the platform can remain lawfully useable in the EU (e.g., by preventing the registration/use of tools which do not meet applicable legal requirements), to ensure the platform's data security (e.g., by preventing the registration/use of tools which may compromise the platform's integrity, or the confidentiality of data stored on the platform), to preserve the platform's trustworthiness (e.g., by preventing the registration/use of tools which do not meet baseline ethical standards, and which thereby present a relevant risk of deriving skewed, biased, inaccurate or otherwise misleading information from the data source to which they are applied) and to prevent potential reputational damages suffered by the Consortium, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and/or PolicyCLOUD users. As such, technical/organisational measures to provide assurances in this respect must also be implemented on the platform.

Specifically regarding [pre-existing analytics tools](#), to assist in ensuring appropriate auditability of all analytics tools leveraged on the PolicyCLOUD platform – which is, as described in the AI-HLEG's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (referenced and further described in [Section 2.1.4](#) of D3.3 [1]), a key ethical consideration for AI-based tools in particular, though this is arguably extensible to all tools – a standard logging service has been implemented in the platform, as a centralised, PolicyCLOUD project-wide component (as reported in [Section 2.3.2](#) of D4.3 [33]). This service may potentially be extended to [additional analytics tools which may be registered for use via the platform](#), though the feasibility of such an extension is yet unclear as of the date of this Deliverable. Other than this, it has been decided, in the context of WP4, that the specific Consortium members responsible for each relevant tool will be engaged to provide information about the training and testing protocols/programs, mechanisms facilitating auditability of AI-based systems (including the traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data used, the logging of processes/outcomes/impacts), the trade-offs between applicable legal/ethical requirements and principles considered during design, and the degree of possibility of false positive/negative correlations, applicable (or to be applied, where relevant) to the tools for which they are responsible. Further information on this will be collected in the final year of the PolicyCLOUD project, and will be used to provide recommendations to the respective Consortium members so as to maximise the assurances provided as to the legal/ethical compliance of such tools.

Specifically regarding [additional analytics tools which may be registered for use via the platform](#), a balance must be struck between maximising legal/ethical compliance and maximising the registrability of analytics tools. Overemphasis on compliance may create an overly restrictive registration process for such tools, which may ultimately compromise the effectiveness of the PolicyCLOUD platform in allowing tools other than those pre-existing to be leveraged; however, overemphasis on registrability triggers all risks related to the failure to meet a high standard of legal/ethical compliance mentioned above. In discussions with WP4, it has been concluded – as described in [Section 2.3.3](#) of D4.3 [33] – that a practical initial answer to this dilemma is the requirement for PolicyCLOUD users seeking to register a tool to document measures taken to address applicable legal/ethical requirements, through adequate fields added to the registration Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by tool registrants include (as reported in [Section 2.1.2](#) of D4.3 [33]):

- *biasDoc*. This parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and file

size range is included), registrants to link bias management information/documentation to the tool upon registration. This should provide details on specific measures taken to address the risk of biases inherent to the functioning of the tool. It could also permit / oblige registrants to upload or indicate one or more test datasets on which the tool can be applied, to demonstrate that resulting bias measurements do not exceed a given maximum (in other words, that the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases are functioning effectively, as intended);

- *tradeoffsDoc*. This parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and file size range is included), registrants to link trade-off management information/documentation to the tool upon registration. This should provide details on the relevant trade-offs encountered in the development of the tool, decisions made concerning the balancing of competing requirements (e.g., result precision vs. fairness) and measures taken to implement and document those decisions.

The input provided by registrants in these (and other) parameters will be linked, on the PolicyCLOUD platform, to the analytics tool upon its successful registration. This can later be accessed by any PolicyCLOUD user wishing to make use of such a tool, thereby providing some degree of assurance to that user regarding its legal/ethical soundness. This should allow the user to make an informed and risk-based decision about whether or not to leverage a given tool, to provide information to relevant stakeholders about the tool if leveraged, and to critically examine the output generated by the tool in the context of their policy-making decisions.

The status of implementation of the requirements concerning analytics compliance, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 3](#) – Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.3.2 Data Security

Under Controls no. 2, 3 and 7 of the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to define and implement adequate technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of analytics tools and data sources hosted on the PolicyCLOUD platform. These measures should be defined as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis. Specific goals to be met by such measures include:

- Ensuring integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data used as input, the functioning of analytics tools, or the output generated by those tools);
- Ensuring confidentiality (e.g., prevention of unauthorised access to, or disclosure of, data, analytics tools or the output of those tools);
- Ensuring availability (e.g., prevention of loss of the ability to promptly access and make legitimate use of data, analytics tools or the output of those tools);
- Restricting unlawful reuse of personal data hosted on the PolicyCLOUD platform (e.g., appropriate access controls, relevant technical and contractual limitations on such reuse);
- Ensuring the ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents affecting the PolicyCLOUD platform.

Data security concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to the PolicyCLOUD platform’s analytics tools and the PolicyCLOUD data repository – are more generally covered in Section 2.1.1 of this Deliverable.

One specific security measure initially addressed thus far on the PolicyCLOUD platform is the logging service, covered previously in Section 2.3.1 of this Deliverable (from the perspective of ensuring compliance with applicable ethical standards). As reported in Section 2.3.2 of D4.3 [33], the implementation of a secure logging service allows, *inter alia*, identification of security threats, analysis suspected incidents (i.e., forensic analysis), monitoring internal policy violations, collection of information on abnormal events and debugging both performance and functional issues, making this critical to ensure the security of the PolicyCLOUD platform. The PolicyCLOUD project-wide logging service implemented provides an initial solution to this issue, which will be further assessed as part of the project’s efforts to harmonise the approach to data security around relevant standards – in particular, ENISA’s (draft) EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme [30].

As for the implementation of specific restrictions on the unlawful reuse of personal data, the Data Governance and Privacy Enforcement mechanism developed for the PolicyCLOUD platform (addressed above, in Section 2.2.3 of this Deliverable, and better described in Section 6.3 of D3.4 [28]) covers also access to the analytics tools and data sources (hosted in the PolicyCLOUD data repository) available via the PolicyCLOUD platform. As mentioned above, in Section 2.2.3 of this Deliverable, these technical access controls should be complemented by contractual limitations on individuals’ ability to process personal data collected and managed via the PolicyCLOUD platform (including any personal data stored in the PolicyCLOUD data repository). The observations made in the mentioned Section of this Deliverable apply, with the necessary adaptations, in this Section.

2.3.3 Data Source Registration

Under Control no. 5 of the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to implement measures which ensure that data sources presented for registration on the PolicyCLOUD platform can be lawfully leveraged by users, in the sense that they are not subject to relevant restrictions (e.g., contractual terms, database copyright protection, database *sui generis* right protection, copyright protection, privacy/data protection requirements) preventing this.

Similarly to the possibility for additional analytics tools to be registered for use via the platform (covered in Section 2.3.1 of this Deliverable), the PolicyCLOUD platform has also been designed to allow for additional data sources to be registered for use via the platform, as described in Sections 2.1.2 and 2.2.2 of D4.3 [33]. As noted in Section 2.2 of D3.3 [1] and Section 2.3.3 of D4.3 [33], applicable legal requirements may restrict the possibility for such additional data sources, which might otherwise be considered useful to the goals of a given PolicyCLOUD user, to be lawfully leveraged by that user. Where a data source is registered on the PolicyCLOUD platform without an indication of such restrictions (or assurances that such restrictions do not exist), use of that data source carries a risk of breach of applicable laws for PolicyCLOUD users – which may ultimately mean that use of the PolicyCLOUD platform as a whole carries such a risk. Furthermore, as noted in Section 2.1.3 of D3.3 [1] and Section 2.3.3 of D4.3 [33], where a given data source has been built with inherent prejudice or biases (e.g., where the data within does not properly represent a target population, by overrepresenting one gender or ethnicity over another, or where the data draws correlations motivated by biases of the data source creator or others), decisions made based on those data sources may ultimately reflect that same prejudice or biases. Inaccurate or incomplete data may ultimately affect the output produced by the PolicyCLOUD platform, causing misleading or erroneous conclusions which may be relied on by PolicyCLOUD users to create policies which, in turn, may create unforeseen and unjustified harmful impact on individuals and communities. It is therefore important – not only to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform can be lawfully leveraged by its users, at least within the EU legal framework, but also to maximise user adherence to the platform and societal acceptability of policies created using the platform – to implement measures which address these risks.

A parallel can be drawn with the considerations made in Section 2.3.1 of this Deliverable, as regarding the registration of additional data sources, a balance must also be struck between maximizing legal/ethical compliance and maximising the registrability of data sources. Overemphasis on compliance may create an overly restrictive registration process for such data sources, which may ultimately compromise the effectiveness of the PolicyCLOUD platform in allowing data sources other than those pre-existing (i.e., those specifically identified by the UC Partners, and subject to specific assessments in the context of the PolicyCLOUD project) to be leveraged; however, overemphasis on registrability triggers the risks related to the failure to meet a high standard of legal/ethical compliance mentioned above. In discussions with WP4, it has also been concluded – as described in Section 2.3.3 of D4.3 [33] – that the practical initial solution described in Section 2.3.1 of this Deliverable can be applied, *mutatis mutandis*, to data source registrants. In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by these registrants include (as reported in Section 2.1.2 of D4.3 [33]):

- *biasDoc*. This parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and file size range is included), registrants to link bias management information/documentation to the data source upon registration. This should provide details on the bias detection methods applied to the data source, the specific biases identified, and the specific measures taken to address any such biases.
- *GDPRDoc*. This parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and file size range is included), registrants to link privacy / data protection management information/documentation to the data source upon registration. This should provide details on whether any personal data is included within the data source and, if so, the measures taken to ensure that the data source can be leveraged via the PolicyCLOUD platform in compliance with the EU privacy/data protection legal framework, as defined by the GDPR and other applicable data protection laws (e.g., to ensure compliance with the principles of lawfulness, transparency and purpose limitation under the GDPR, considering the purposes for which the personal data within the data source were originally collected and the purposes for which those personal data will be further processed via the platform).
- *authDoc*. This parameter, permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and file size range is included), registrants to link information/documentation to confirm and/or demonstrate that the registration of the data source has been authorised by relevant rightsholders (or that such authorisation is not required under the EU legal framework).

The input provided by registrants in these (and other) parameters will be linked, on the PolicyCLOUD platform, to the data source upon its successful registration. This can later be accessed by any PolicyCLOUD user wishing to make use of such a data source, thereby providing some degree of assurance to that user regarding its legal/ethical soundness. This should allow the user to make an informed and risk-based decision about whether or not to leverage a given data source, to provide information to relevant stakeholders about the data source if leveraged, and to critically examine the output generated from the data source in the context of their policy-making decisions.

The status of implementation of the requirements concerning data source registration, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 3](#) – Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.3.4 Data Subjects' Rights

Under Control no. 6 of the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform allows for the exercise of Data Subject Rights – at a minimum, the platform should not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights. As reported in Sections 2.2.4.3 and 2.2.4.7 of D3.3 [1], the GDPR's principle of fairness requires the Consortium to ensure that the PolicyCLOUD platform is designed and implemented in such a manner that it is capable of facilitating the exercise of these rights (by having effective mechanisms in place to allow for this), and the GDPR's principle of accuracy specifies this by affording those individuals the general right to an overview of, and easy access to, their personal data which is processed via the platform, to allow them to control its accuracy and rectify it as needed. This requires the Consortium to ensure that the platform (and, in particular, the PolicyCLOUD data repository) allows the querying of any such data to identify, extract, modify and/or delete personal data pertaining to an individual.

To assist the Consortium in meeting these requirements concerning individuals whose personal data may be included in data sources processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform, the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist** was expanded to include a description of the rights afforded to individuals under the GDPR, and an indication of the technical abilities which the PolicyCLOUD platform should allow (either under individuals' autonomous control, or under the control of platform system administrators) to ensure that these rights can be appropriately exercised. This description is equivalent to that provided in Table 3 – WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist: Data Subject Rights of Section 2.2.4 of this Deliverable.

The status of implementation of specific requirements concerning the implementation of measures to ensure the exercise of Data Subject Rights, concerning individuals whose personal data may be included in data sources processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see Annex 3 – Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

The implementation of these requirements concerning PolicyCLOUD users is addressed in Section 2.2.4 of this Deliverable.

2.3.5 Data Quality (Minimisation, Retention, Accuracy)

Under Controls no. 8 and 9 of the **WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, it is necessary to ensure that, where personal data is included in a data source which is to be processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform, only those personal data which are adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the specific purpose(s) for which the data source is to be processed are actually collected and further stored on the platform. This requires the amount of personal data collected from each data source to be minimised to the greatest extent possible – in particular, if it is possible to process a data source in compliance with a PolicyCLOUD user's purposes without collecting personal data, this should be done. This implies also that any personal data stored on the platform, in a form which permits the identification of the individuals to which it relates, should not be stored in such a form for any longer than necessary to allow the purposes for its lawful collection/further processing to be met. In other words, specific retention periods for such personal data, defined considering the purposes for which such data are used, should be implemented in the PolicyCLOUD project and on the platform – where a retention period is exceeded, the personal data to which it relates should be erased or, alternatively, anonymised (e.g., via aggregation), unless a legal basis can be identified, under the GDPR, for its further retention. Furthermore, appropriate steps must be taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data which is ultimately collected and stored on the platform, and to maintain the accuracy of such personal data over time.

As specified in Section 2.2.4.6 of D3.3 [1] and Section 2.3.3 of D4.3 [33], the GDPR's principle of data minimisation requires the processing of personal data to be avoided altogether whenever feasible (favouring the use of aggregated or fully anonymised data, if this does not substantially compromise the goals for which the processing of personal data was intended), or otherwise that such personal data be minimised, through techniques such as pseudonymisation and/or limitations on the amount of personal data collected and used. Furthermore, the GDPR's principle of accuracy requires not only the implementation of mechanisms to ensure that concerned data subjects are able to request the rectification of any of their personal data stored on the PolicyCLOUD platform which may be inaccurate or incomplete (see Section 2.3.4 of this Deliverable), but also mechanisms to ensure that any personal data collected and further stored on the platform is as accurate and complete as possible. As reported in Section 3.2.2.1 of D4.3, mandatory and optional data constraints can be defined to configure the parameters under which the data validation, cleaning and verification activities (addressed above, in Section 2.3.1 of this Deliverable, and better described in Section 3.2.2 of D4.3) operate. This should, as reported in discussions held with the relevant WP4 Partners (and also in Section 2.1.2 of D4.3), afford control to PolicyCLOUD users over the specific data points of a data source to be registered and leveraged via the PolicyCLOUD platform. This will allow users to configure the platform so that personal data is not unnecessarily collected or processed (i.e., allowing users to prevent or minimise the collection/processing of personal data, such as by refraining from requiring the collection/processing of relevant identifiers), thereby allowing unnecessary personal data to be removed from data sources prior to their further storage and processing via the PolicyCLOUD platform. Furthermore, as noted in Section 3.2.2 of D4.3, various libraries are exploited in connection with the platform's data validation, cleaning and verification

activities to provide greater assurances of data quality (including accuracy, completeness and lack of errors).

Data retention concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to data sources stored on the PolicyCLOUD platform – are more generally covered in [Section 2.1.2](#) of this Deliverable.

In order to ensure that, concerning personal data related to individuals whose personal data may be included in data sources processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform, after a defined retention period is exceeded, such personal data can be effectively erased or anonymised, the ability to erase or anonymise such personal data (either automatically, or manually) must be implemented.

The status of implementation of specific requirements concerning data quality, regarding data sources which are registered and further leveraged via the PolicyCLOUD platform, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 3](#) – Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.4 Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management (WP5)

2.4.1 PolicyCLOUD user-facing tools (PDT, PME)

The Policy Development Toolkit (PDT), as better described in [Section 5](#) of D5.4 [2], is a web-based tool which includes a front-end, allowing policy makers to evaluate Policy Models (PMs), and a back-end that hides the complexity of storing the data models into persistent storage and implements the services that the front-end uses to display the content to the user and provide the necessary User Experience (UX). Concerning the back-end, data storage and analytics have been addressed in previous sections.⁸

On the other end, the Policy Model Editor (PME) is a tool which links with the PolicyCLOUD platform's front-end. The purpose of the PME is to allow the creation of new policies and editing of existing ones following an evaluation process. As described in [Section 3.2.2](#) of D5.4 [2], the PME helps PolicyCLOUD users to create Public Policies (PPs) by applying relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are stored into the PDT backend (or by composing new KPIs through the definition of actors and stakeholders in the PM), selecting the relevant data source(s) and analytics tools to be applied to that data source(s), and finally setting the parameter values that those tools require to provide the result and save the PM to the PolicyCLOUD data repository.

From a contractual perspective, as noted in [Section 3.3](#) of D3.3 [1], it is important to define terms and conditions for the use of the PDT and PME, so as to properly regulate the service relationship established between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and tool users (i.e., individual users, or organisations to which the individual users belong). These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for the use of the PDT/PME to be allowed. Matters which should be regulated include:

1. Description of services offered through the PDT and the PME;
2. Payment terms (if applicable);
3. Acceptable use of the PDT and the PME;
4. Intellectual property (in particular, ownership of the PDT/PME's assets, the input provided by users via the PDT/PME, and the output generated by the PDT/PME);
5. Data protection (with reference to the privacy policy⁹, as well as to a data processing agreement or similar arrangement which may be put in place between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and the PDT/PME users).

⁸See [Sections 2.2 and 2.3](#) of this Deliverable.

⁹See [Section 2.4.2](#) of this Deliverable.

6. Warranties provided by the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and liability terms related to provision of the PDT/PME, considering the likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in PDT/PME output and the possibility for such output to be used to create public policies;
7. Warranties provided by PDT/PME users, in particular regarding compliance with ethical and legal requirements around selection of data sources and use of the PDT/PME for policy-making purposes;
8. Applicable law;
9. Terms under which the terms and conditions may be modified; and
10. Termination and effects of termination.

The status of implementation of terms and conditions concerning the PDT/PME, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 4](#) – Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

2.4.2 Data Management

It is important to note that information on PDT/PME users will typically be collected and stored in the PDT backend for a variety of purposes (e.g., user authentication). This information will be classifiable as personal data to the extent that it can be traced back to an individual user and thus the following concerns have been or are being addressed:

- (1) **Lawfulness**. An appropriate legal basis for each purpose for which personal data on users may be collected has been identified, under Art. 6 GDPR. All steps needed to properly implement the identified legal bases have been taken, depending on the legal bases selected, which in turn depends on the way user personal data are processed via the PDT. The legal bases are:
 - Compliance with legal requirements, under Art. 6(1)(c) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and users (or the organisations to which users belong) to ensure the proper operation of the PDT/PME and overall PolicyCLOUD platform, under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and users (or the organisations to which users belong) to ensure the security of the PDT/PME and overall PolicyCLOUD platform, as well as of data stored on the platform, under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR;
 - The legitimate interests of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) in leveraging personal data as needed for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims (e.g., brought against the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) for damages resulting from use of the PDT/PME), under Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR.
- (2) **Fairness**. Personal data on users is not used in a manner which may violate their reasonable expectations. Users are not profiled, and their data is not covertly shared with third parties for marketing purposes. Also, mechanisms are in place to ensure that users can exercise their rights

in relation to any personal data of theirs which may be collected during the use of the PDT/PME. More specifically, each data subject will be able to exercise the following rights by sending a request in writing to the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s), to the extent permitted by applicable law:

- To access. Data subjects can obtain information relating to the processing of their personal data and a copy of such personal data;
- To erase. Data subjects can require the deletion of their personal data, to the extent permitted by law;
- To object. Data subjects can object to the processing of their personal data, on grounds relating to their situation. Where an objection is presented, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) will be entitled to assess the request, and refuse the request if there are legitimate reasons to proceed with the processing that prevail over the freedoms, interests, and rights of the requesting data subject;
- To rectify. Where data subjects consider that their personal data is inaccurate or incomplete, they can require that such personal data be modified accordingly;
- To restrict. Data subjects can request the restriction of the processing of their personal data.

Furthermore, should data subjects believe that the processing of their personal data is contrary to the legislation in force, they have the right to lodge a complaint to the competent data protection supervisory authority.

- (3) Transparency. A specific privacy policy has been developed for the PDT, to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the PDT in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR. An initial version of this privacy policy for the PDT – which is arguably extensible, with minor adaptations, to other platforms relevant to the Project, such as the PME or the Incentives Management tool – is attached to D8.1 [3]. This document will be further revised with the Consortium and adapted over time, as part of the ongoing implementation of the legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements identified in D3.3 [1] and in this Deliverable - progress on this will be reported in the upcoming D3.9 Deliverable. More specifically, the data protection information notice is provided to PDT users using a two-layer approach:

- The first layer is represented by a pop-up banner which is shown to users when accessing the PDT. This pop-up banner includes a link to the second layer data protection information notice (i.e., the extended version of the data protection information notice). The text of the pop-up banner is provided in D8.1. See also Figure 1 for more details.

Policy Cloud

Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

The Policy Cloud project aims to harness the potential of digitisation, big data and cloud technologies to *improve the modelling, creation and implementation of policy*.

Funded under the European Commission's H2020 programme, the project will deliver a unique, integrated environment of curated datasets and data management, manipulation, and analysis tools addressing the full lifecycle of policy management using the data analysis capabilities of the European Cloud Initiative.

Please press **Login** to continue. You will be directed to our Authentication Server.

Login

For the main purpose of creating and managing your account and of operating this platform, the PolicyCLOUD project consortium processes personal data related to you. Please click [here](#) to see the detailed data protection information notice on the processing of your personal data.

FIGURE 1 – POP-UP BANNER

- The second layer is represented by the extended version of the data protection information notice, including all elements required by Arts 13 and 14 GDPR. This extended version of the data protection information notice, the text of which is provided under D8.1 [3], is accessible to PDT users by clicking on a footer named “End Users Data Protection Information Notice” published on all the pages of the PDT’s web environment. See also Figure 2 and Figure 3 for more details.

POLICYCLOUD – END USERS DATA PROTECTION INFORMATION NOTICE

The PolicyCLOUD project consortium (“**PolicyCLOUD**”), according to the provisions of Regulation EU No. 2016/679 (“General Data Protection Regulation” - “**GDPR**”), provides the following information on the processing of the personal data (the “**Data**”) of the end users of the PolicyCLOUD platform (the “**Platform**”).

Who we are and what Data we process?

PolicyCLOUD is the controller of the Data of the end users of the Platform. PolicyCLOUD can be reached by sending a written communication to info@policycloud.eu, or via the contact forms available on the website policycloud.eu.

The Data of the end users of the Platform processed by PolicyCLOUD are the following:

- name.
- e-mail address.
- organization and role.
- username and password.
- IP address.
- event logs related to the use of the Platform.

The Data can be provided to PolicyCLOUD by both the end user and their organization.

Why we process the Data and on which legal basis?

The Data is used by PolicyCLOUD for the following purposes:

- Creation and management of the end user account and operation of the Platform. The use of the Data is

FIGURE 2 – END USERS DATA PROTECTION INFORMATION NOTICE

End Users Data Protection Information Notice

© Copyright 2020-2021 – Policy Cloud has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 870675.

FIGURE 3 – END USERS DATA PROTECTION INFORMATION NOTICE (FOOTER)

Additionally, it is important to note that the PDT and PME do not use cookies or similar tracking technologies, so no specific compliance requirements are needed to this regard.

- (4) Purpose limitation. Personal data collected on PDT/PME users is not used for purposes which are incompatible with those declared in the privacy policy, which are:

- Creation and management of the end user account and operation of the platform.
 - Ensuring the security and the proper use of the platform.
 - To defend PolicyCLOUD from legal and/or regulatory risks.
- (5) *Data minimisation.* Only the strict minimum amount of personal data needed for the above listed purposes are collected. More specifically, the personal data of PDT/PME users processed are the following:
- Name;
 - E-mail address;
 - Organisation and role;
 - Username and password;
 - IP address;
 - Event logs related to the use of the platform.
- (6) *Accuracy.* Users are given the possibility to rectify any personal data they submit, or which is collected on them, in connection with use of the PDT/PME, by sending a request in writing to PolicyCLOUD;
- (7) *Storage limitation.* Personal data on PDT/PME users may only be stored for the strict minimum amount of time needed to meet any of the purposes for which they were lawfully collected, after which the personal data should be irreversibly anonymised or deleted. This requires the identification of appropriate retention periods for any such personal data collected.¹⁰
- (8) *Security.* Appropriate security measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of any collected and further stored personal data, as well as the resilience of systems used to collect and further store those data, must be implemented.¹¹
- (9) *Accountability.* Records of evidence showing compliance with these requirements must be kept.

Furthermore, when offering the PDT and/or PME as a service, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) may be acting, simultaneously, as a controller for some activities involving personal data and as a processor on behalf of the end-users. As such, entering a standard DPA under Art. 28 GDPR may not suffice to fully regulate the data processing relationship between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and PDT users, as this would only cover the processor activities of the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s). To comprehensively regulate this relationship, the arrangement will need to include obligations to govern the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) personal data processing activities as a controller. This can be done through a Data Management Agreement (DMA, which distinguishes between the different sets of processing activities performed and allocates different corresponding sets of obligations to each party, to ensure that it is clear to what extent each party will be responsible for complying with the different controller obligations laid out in the GDPR.

Finally, the data visualisation components of the PDT should, as mentioned in [Section 3.3](#) of D3.3 [1], ideally not actually rely on or disclose information about identifiable individuals, but instead rely on

¹⁰See [Section 2.1.2](#) of this Deliverable.

¹¹See [Section 2.1.1](#) of this Deliverable.

appropriately aggregated data, which cannot be traced back to any given specific and identified individual, to avoid raising personal data protection concerns regarding data manipulated by PDT users. Where this is feasible, the core concerns around data visualisation shall focus on:

- (1) *Statistical accuracy.* Indeed, a failure to provide appropriate visualisation results may ultimately lead to misleading or erroneous conclusions drawn by policymakers, culminating in misguided policy-making activities. As such, the Consortium should ensure that enough testing is performed to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for these activities. Any operations performed on data should be methodically logged to ensure traceability, and the general rationale and logic behind the data visualisation should be explained to PDT users, so this can be considered during their decision-making process. Users should be advised of the possibility of false positives or false negatives and errors in result presentation, so that they are incentivised to critically examine results produced by the visualisation functions in their decision-making process.¹²
- (2) *Explainability of results.* For a PDT user to make use of the PDT in a meaningful way, as a tool to support policymaking while preserving their own accountability for the decisions taken regarding any specific policy, it is important that they can understand the output presented to them by the PDT. Several different means can be conceived of to provide this information to users. The most appropriate form of delivery, considering the UX and context when operating the PDT, should be further assessed. Clear explanations should be given to users on:
 - Steps taken across the design and implementation of the PDT and overall PolicyCLOUD platform to ensure compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements, in particular those implemented to maximise the security and robustness of the platform, as well as the accuracy and reliability of output;
 - The types of data sources and data used to produce outputs;
 - The rationale behind outputs, in terms of explaining generically how the data sources and data were processed to generate the outputs in question;
 - The likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in the outputs and the importance of critical examination and validation of output implications for policymaking by the user.

The status of implementation of data management requirements concerning the PDT/PME, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 4](#) – Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

¹²The same considerations as developed for analytics functions in [Section 2.3.1](#) of this Deliverable apply, with the necessary adaptations.

2.5 Use Cases Adaptation, Integration & Experimentation (WP6)

2.5.1 Data Source Selection

2.5.1.1 UC #1: PARTICIPATORY POLICIES AGAINST RADICALIZATION

UC #1 is developing a collaborative data-driven analysis for the validation of existing policies against radicalisation, based on a participatory review of data collected from social media (e.g., Reddit, Really Simple Syndication [RSS] feeds, Twitter) and open datasets (e.g., the Global Terrorism Database [GTD] and RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism). In addition, it will provide useful insights and valuable information to policy makers at any level (local, regional, national, and EU level) which can be used to update current policies and/or create new ones, while at the same time allowing them to interact with other relevant stakeholders (i.e., Law Enforcement Agencies [LEAs], social services, schools, civil society) during the creation and modelling of new policies and specific countermeasures, ranging from early detection methodologies to techniques and policies for the monitoring and management of domestic radicalisation. [4]

UC #1's objectives are to improve operational efficiency, transparency, and decision making through the PolicyCLOUD platform's big data streaming and real-time big data analysis functionalities. The visualisation technologies available on the platform will enable policy makers to identify issues and trends, as well as assess policy effects and interactions. The PolicyCLOUD platform's analytics tools will enable users to discover insights and find meaningful explanations about the effects of policies. [4]

SCENARIO A: RADICALIZATION INCIDENTS

UC #1's Scenario A aims to monitor the occurrence of radicalisation incidents in the geographic proximity of a region. Data coming from the GTD and RAND are used. The policy maker can select an area of interest and consult the different incidents that have taken place within that area during a specific period. The goals of this scenario are to validate existing policies and determine, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones. [4]

For this scenario, the data sources which have been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], are:

- Dataset 7 (GTD), an open-source database including information on domestic and international terrorist attacks around the world taking place between 1970 and 2018, which now includes more than 190,000 cases; [6]
- Dataset 8 (the RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism Incidents [RDWTI]), an open-source database including information of international and domestic terrorism incidents taking place between 1968 and 2009, which now includes more than 40,000 cases. [7]

The use of these data sources does not raise specific legal/regulatory or ethical/societal concerns, provided that the data sources are used in accordance with their respective licensing terms and conditions:

- The GTD's End User License Agreement (EULA) defines the conditions under which the GTD can be accessed and used to conduct research and analysis for non-commercial purposes. [8] It is necessary to ensure that the use of this data source, in the course of the PolicyCLOUD project, is strictly aligned with the conditions set by this EULA.
- The RDWTI is publicly available. As stated on RAND's website, everyone is welcome to use this database; however, all public use of these data must be attributed to the "RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism Incidents." [9] It is necessary to ensure compliance with this attribution requirement.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #1's Scenario A, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 5](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario A to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO B: RADICALIZED GROUPS AND INDIVIDUALS

UC #1's Scenario B aims to identify the main actors (individuals or groups) involved in extremism activities or propaganda spreading, through online and offline activities. Data coming from the GTD and RAND will be used. PolicyCLOUD users will be able to select the individuals or groups active in an area of interest and consult different incidents linked to each individual/group. As with Scenario A, the goals of this scenario are to validate existing policies and determine, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones. [4]

For this scenario, the data sources which have been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5] are the same as in Scenario A. The same considerations as to applicable legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements as drawn for Scenario A apply.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #1's Scenario B, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 6](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario B to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO C: TREND ANALYSIS

UC #1's Scenario C aims to identify current and future trends related to radicalisation efforts, through keyword detection, new entity recognition and new term identification. Data collected from social media will be used. PolicyCLOUD users will be able to select keywords of interest and consult information linked to those keywords. As with Scenarios A and B, the goals of this scenario are to validate existing policies and determine, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones. [4]

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Twitter (i.e., Dataset 4: relevant Twitter posts published by users, captured, and processed for subsequent analysis in UC #1).

From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the use of this data source, in the context of Scenario C, raises the following points of attention:

- (1) The relevant Use Case Partner should carefully assess Twitter's terms and conditions, to ensure that data collected from Twitter can be leveraged for the purposes of this scenario. A thorough analysis of Twitter's general and specific terms and conditions (i.e., Twitter's general terms of use, or more specific terms of use which may be available for use of Twitter for professional purposes, potentially covering the use of APIs connected to Twitter) is necessary, to ensure that this data source can be leveraged for these purposes without breach of any contractual obligations;
- (2) In particular, it should be noted that Twitter's terms of service [10] specify that a third party may not access or search or attempt to access or search Twitter's services by any means (automated or otherwise) other than through currently available, published interfaces that are provided by Twitter (and only pursuant to the applicable terms and conditions), unless the third party has been specifically allowed to do so in a separate agreement with Twitter. It is also specified that crawling Twitter's services is permissible if done in accordance with the provisions of Twitter's robots.txt file¹³; however, scraping Twitter's services without Twitter's prior consent is expressly prohibited;
- (3) Similarly, the Use Case Partner should assess whether this data source, or any relevant parts of this data source which are to be processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform under this scenario, may be qualified as a protected database under Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (the "**Database Directive**"), under copyright, or under *sui generis* protection, under the local laws applicable to the Use Case Partner (or the PolicyCLOUD users for which this scenario is intended). Where this is the case, the Use Case partner should assess whether any authorisations from relevant

¹³ Robots.txt is a file used by websites to let bots know if or how the website should be scrapped or crawled and indexed.

- rightsholders (e.g., Twitter, Twitter users) is required under those laws, and obtain such authorisations if needed;
- (4) The information available related to this scenario strongly implies that the leveraging of this data source will involve the processing of personal data. This will, in particular, be the case where tweets, or other Twitter content, are collected in a form which allows their poster, uploader, or sharer to be identified (e.g., through their name, online handle, or other potential identifiers included in the content). The relevant privacy / data protection compliance obligations which may be triggered as a result are further described in [Section 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable;
 - (5) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #1's Scenario C, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 7](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario C to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO D: (NEAR) REAL-TIME ASSESSMENT OF ONLINE PROPAGANDA

UC #1's Scenario D aims at providing the ability to understand the context of specific events and online activities (through techniques such as sentiment analysis, opinion mining, location surveillance, and user monitoring). Data collected from social media will be used. As with Scenario C, PolicyCLOUD users will be able to select keywords of interest and consult information linked to those keywords. As with the remaining scenarios of UC #1, the goals of this scenario are to validate existing policies and determine, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones. [4]

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is the same as in Scenario C. The same considerations as to applicable legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements as drawn for Scenario C apply.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #1's Scenario D, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 8](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario D to this Deliverable.

2.5.1.2 UC #2: INTELLIGENT POLICIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRI-FOOD INDUSTRY

UC #2 aims at achieving the following main objectives [4]:

- (1) Improving investments in agri-food promotion by the Government of Aragon;
- (2) Facilitating tools and access to new technologies for small and medium producers, tools based on open data, social media analysis, and opinion mining;
- (3) Improving the distribution of products thanks to the tools created through the PolicyCLOUD project, which will allow the searching and comparing of prices, as well as the positioning of PolicyCLOUD users' products (and those of their competitors);
- (4) Supporting decision-making regarding investment in different geographical areas with market study elements based on AI;
- (5) Bringing the agri-food industry closer to new technologies;
- (6) Supporting policy makers in the design and modelling of new policies and/or updating existing ones;
- (7) Creating stable working groups between producers and policy makers which allow the improvement of communication channels and the development of new tools.

SCENARIO A: PRICE OF WINE

UC #2's Scenario A aims to visualise the sale price of wine on different specialised websites, with automatic warning systems to assist PolicyCLOUD users in avoiding penalties related to contracts with large distributors. The goal of this scenario is to facilitate the monitoring of distribution prices for PolicyCLOUD users' own products and those of the competition, allowing users to improve their commercial policies. [4]

From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the data sources used in this scenario raise the following points of attention:

- (1) The relevant Use Case Partner should carefully assess terms and conditions applicable to each website and/or e-commerce platform selected as a data source, to ensure that data collected from those data sources can be leveraged for the purposes of this scenario. A thorough analysis of the general and specific terms and conditions linked to each data source is necessary, to ensure that those data sources can be leveraged for these purposes without breach of any contractual obligations;
- (2) Similarly, the Use Case Partner should assess whether these data sources, or any relevant parts of these data sources which are to be processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform under this scenario, may be qualified as a protected database under Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (the "**Database Directive**"), under copyright, or under *sui generis* protection, under the local laws applicable to the Use Case Partner (or the PolicyCLOUD users for which this scenario is intended). Where this is the case, the Use Case partner should assess whether any authorisations from relevant rightsholders (e.g., owners of the websites/e-commerce platforms) is required under

- those laws, and obtain such authorisations if needed. This assessment will arguably need to be carried out per each individual data source;
- (3) The information available related to this scenario suggests (though this is not clear) that the leveraging of these data sources (or of some of these data sources) will involve the processing of personal data. The relevant privacy / data protection compliance obligations which may be triggered as a result are further described in [Section 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable;
 - (4) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #2's Scenario A, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 9](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario A to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO B: OPINIONS ON SOCIAL NETWORKS

UC #2's Scenario B aims at visualising opinions posted on social media regarding different products, allowing PolicyCLOUD users to generate automatic and immediate responses to social media users. The goal of this scenario is to create a process for immediate communication with social media users, with insight into their opinions regarding the relevant product(s) (whether positive or negative), to allow more direct interaction with those social media users. [4]

From an ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal standpoint, the data sources used in this scenario raise the following points of attention:

- (1) The relevant Use Case Partner should carefully assess terms and conditions applicable to each relevant social media platform (i.e., Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and Twitter), to ensure that data collected from those data sources can be leveraged for the purposes of this scenario. A thorough analysis of the general and specific terms and conditions linked to each data source (i.e., general terms of use, or more specific terms of use which may be available for use of the relevant platforms for professional purposes, potentially covering the use of APIs connected to those platforms) is necessary, to ensure that those data sources can be leveraged for these purposes without breach of any contractual obligations;
- (2) In particular, it should be noted that Twitter's terms of service [10] specify that a third party may not access or search or attempt to access or search Twitter's services by any means (automated or otherwise) other than through currently available, published interfaces that are provided by Twitter (and only pursuant to the applicable terms and conditions), unless the third party has been specifically allowed to do so in a separate agreement with Twitter. It is also specified that crawling Twitter's services is permissible if done in accordance with the provisions of Twitter's

- robots.txt file¹⁴; however, scraping Twitter’s services without Twitter’s prior consent is expressly prohibited.
- (3) Similarly, under Facebook’s terms of service [11], it is forbidden to access or collect data on Facebook using automated means without prior permission from Facebook and, provided that an agreement with Facebook is entered, it is nevertheless necessary to comply with specific terms governing the automated data collection. [12]
 - (4) LinkedIn’s User Agreement [13] also explicitly states that users may not “*Develop, support or use software, devices, scripts, robots or any other means or processes (including crawlers, browser plugins and add-ons or any other technology) to scrape the Services or otherwise copy profiles and other data from the Services*”, which suggests the need for a separate agreement or authorisation from LinkedIn in order to be able to do so.
 - (5) The Use Case Partner should assess whether these data sources, or any relevant parts of these data sources which are to be processed via the PolicyCLOUD platform under this scenario, may be qualified as a protected database under Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (the “**Database Directive**”), under copyright, or under *sui generis* protection, under the local laws applicable to the Use Case Partner (or the PolicyCLOUD users for which this scenario is intended). Where this is the case, the Use Case partner should assess whether any authorisations from relevant rightsholders (e.g., social media platform providers or users) is required under those laws, and obtain such authorisations if needed;
 - (6) The information available related to this scenario strongly implies that the leveraging of this data source will involve the processing of personal data. This will, in particular, be the case where posts, or other social media content, are collected in a form which allows their poster, uploader, or sharer to be identified (e.g., through their name, online handle, or other potential identifiers included in the content). The relevant privacy / data protection compliance obligations which may be triggered as a result are further described in [Section 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable;
 - (5) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #2’s Scenario B, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 10](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario B to this Deliverable.

¹⁴ Robots.txt is a file used by websites to let bots know if or how the website should be scrapped or crawled and indexed.

SCENARIO C: TREND ANALYSIS

UC #2's Scenario C aims to analyse trends in the wine sector, by analysing specialised websites related to this sector, so as to draw insight on trends in each market of interest to the PolicyCLOUD user and allow the adjustment of diffusion policies accordingly. [4]

From an ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal standpoint, the data sources used in this scenario raise the same points of attention as described for UC #2's Scenario A (with the necessary adaptations).

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #2's Scenario C, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 11](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario C to this Deliverable.

2.5.1.3 UC #3: FACILITATING URBAN POLICY MAKING AND MONITORING THROUGH CROWDSOURCING DATA ANALYSIS

UC #3 aims at achieving the following main objectives [4]:

- (1) Supporting the Use Case Partner's urban policy making in key areas for the city of Sofia;
- (2) Supporting PolicyCLOUD users in the design and modelling of new policies and/or updating of existing policies, by enhancing their knowledge and capability to identify problems, issues and trends related to urban environments;
- (3) Supporting PolicyCLOUD users in the adoption or modification of adequate policy making decisions on budget planning and effective use of budget and public resources;
- (4) Enhancing the Use Case Partner's operational efficiency, transparency, and decision-making, to improve the overall quality of life in the city of Sofia;
- (5) Using visualisation tools to support PolicyCLOUD users in identifying issues, trends, and tendencies (including behavioural trends), and policy effects and interactions;
- (6) Validating existing policies and assess potential policies and initiatives in focus areas;
- (7) Facilitating more efficient use of resources;
- (8) Sharing best practices and lessons learned with relevant stakeholders (at any level).

SCENARIO 1: ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE

UC #3's Scenario 1 aims to visualise signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia") related to road infrastructure and adjacent urban infrastructure and to provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas, districts and major transport roads), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Improvement of long-term policy making in the area of road infrastructure;
- (2) Improvement of district administrations' and the municipal administration's envisioning and capacity-building regarding the solving of road infrastructure-related problems;
- (3) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality.

From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the data source used in this scenario raises the following points of attention:

- (1) The information available related to this scenario strongly implies that the leveraging of this data source will involve the processing of personal data. The relevant privacy / data protection compliance obligations which may be triggered as a result are further described in [Section 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable;
- (2) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented.

Given that the Use Case Partner is also responsible for the management of the data source, there are no applicable contractual or intellectual property-related restrictions applicable to the leveraging of this data source in the context of this scenario.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 1, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 12](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 1 to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO 2: ENVIRONMENT AND AIR QUALITY

UC #3's Scenario 2 aims to visualise signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia"), as well as additional data provided by the Air Things air monitoring platform, to provide a detailed analysis of the signals related to air quality, their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas and districts), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Improvement of long-term policy making in the area of air quality and, by extension, in other environmental areas related to air quality;
- (2) Improvement of the long-term health and quality of life of Sofia's citizens;
- (3) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data sources which have been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], are:

- (1) Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality;
- (2) Dataset 19 (Sofia Municipality Airthings Platform), i.e., real time Internet of Things (IoT) sensors data for monitoring and measurement of the air quality. [14]

From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the first data source identified (Dataset 18) raises the same points of attention as in Scenario 1. As for the second data source identified (Dataset 19):

- (1) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented. In this respect, specific provisions of the Airthings terms and conditions [15] should be borne in mind, such as the fact that Airthings does not warrant the accuracy of data collected, the possibility for Airthings to apply rate limiting to traffic or quotas to API usage, and the possibility for Airthings to introduce new API updates and versions at its discretion, all of which create risks to the accuracy and availability of data collected through the API.

Concerning Dataset 19, from a contractual standpoint, the Use Case Partner- is generally authorised to use Airthings data in the context of this scenario, as the terms made available by Airthings online (Section 4 of the Specific Terms for Subscription Services) state that "*Airthings grants the Customer a limited, nonexclusive, non-sublicensable, non-transferable license under intellectual property rights to use the Airthings application programming interface ("Airthings API") for the purpose of developing and implementing customer specific software solutions, products and applications integrating with products and services*". [15] Additionally, leveraging this data source will not imply the processing of personal data,

except for personal data on specific individuals authorised by the Use Case Partner to operate the Airthings API. [16]

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 2, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 13](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 2 to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO 3: WASTE COLLECTION AND WASTE DISPOSAL

UC #3's Scenario 3 aims to visualise the signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia") related to waste collection and waste disposal, as well as to provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas and districts), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Identification of more efficient ways and methods of waste collection;
- (2) Improvement of long-term planning and policy making related to waste collection and waste disposal using smart meters;
- (3) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality. From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the identified data source raises the same points of attention as in Scenario 1.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 3, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 14](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 3 to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO 4: TRANSPORT AND PARKING

UC #3's Scenario 4 aims to visualise the signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia") related to transport and parking, and to provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas and districts), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Improvement of the quality of transport and parking services;
- (2) Improvement of transport times and allowing better connections for citizens;
- (3) Assessment of multimodal pricing schemes and initiatives such as "Green Ticket";
- (4) Adoption of quantity measures for better parking management;
- (5) Improvement of overall parking capabilities;
- (6) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality. From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the identified data source raises the same points of attention as in Scenario 1.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 4, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 15](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 4 to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO 5: CLEANLINESS OF PUBLIC SPACES

UC #3's Scenario 5 aims to visualise the signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia") related to cleanliness of public spaces and to provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas and districts), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Improvement of the overall level of cleanliness of public spaces;
- (2) Improvement of planning and adoption and/or modification of current measures to ensure cleaner public spaces and the overall improvement of the urban environment;
- (3) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality. From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the identified data source raises the same points of attention as in Scenario 1.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 5, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 16](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 5 to this Deliverable.

SCENARIO 6: VIOLATION OF PUBLIC ORDER

UC #3's Scenario 5 aims to visualise the signals received via Sofia's Call Centre ("CallSofia") related to public order violations and to provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution based on various parameters (e.g., categories, types, areas and districts), in order to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making. [4] The goals of this scenario are:

- (1) Improvement of long-term policies related to violation prevention and maintaining of public order.
- (2) Validation of existing policies and determination, based on the retrieved information, whether there is a need to update existing policies or create new ones.

For this scenario, the data source which has been identified as relevant, as reported in D1.3 [5], is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality. From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the identified data source raises the same points of attention as in Scenario 1.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #3's Scenario 5, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 17](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 6 to this Deliverable.

2.5.1.4 UC #4: PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS TOWARDS UNEMPLOYMENT RISKS IDENTIFICATION AND POLICY MAKING

UC #4 aims to assist policy makers in creating effective policies that will address employment figures in the Camden Borough of London. The overall goal of this UC is for policy makers to be able to use statistics from predictive algorithms provided by the PolicyCLOUD platform to assist in making decisions during the policy creation process. The main objective will be to design algorithms that will help predict future trends using relevant data sources (i.e., unemployment datasets).

The scenarios related to this UC are described in [Table 6](#) – UC #4 Scenarios

Scenario	Description	Goals
A – Citizens Affected by Unemployment	Conduct analysis based off the statistics on specific time periods. For example, the unemployment is expected to go up during the year 2022 due to the current pandemic. Therefore, the statistics recorded against the current year can help to identify the possible unemployment rate if there is second wave of infections the following year.	The goal of this scenario is to use the analytics and visualisations produced from the PolicyCLOUD platform to identify key information that could help determine groups of citizens that are affected by unemployment.
B – Predictive Analysis	Using predictive analysis to predict a future outcome.	The goal of this scenario is to use specially designed algorithms from PolicyCLOUD to predict future outcomes.
C – Trends Analysis	Analysis of the trends in the public sector based on specific regions.	This action will allow us to know the trends in each of the markets that are of interest, knowing the trends regarding employment and local citizens.

TABLE 6 – UC #4 SCENARIOS

For all of these scenarios, the relevant data source identified in D1.3 [5] is Dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count), retrieved from the Open Data Camden platform, which allows the general public, researchers and developers to access, analyse and share information about the Camden Borough. [17] All data available on this platform is authorised to be viewed, re-used, and downloaded under an Open Government License (OGL). [18] Datasets are accessible through the main catalogue or by the categories through the platform, which contains various open datasets based on air quality, local government spending, planning permissions, and more. The data related to unemployment available on the platform consists of different types of benefits, which include registered individuals, Jobseekers Allowance (JSA) claimants and Universal Credit claimants who are actively seeking work. [19]

From a legal/regulatory and ethical/societal standpoint, the data source used in this scenario raises the following points of attention:

- (1) Under the terms of the relevant OGL License [18], the Use Case Partner must acknowledge the data source by including or linking to any attribution statement specified by the information provider(s) and, where possible, providing a link to the OGL License, as well as including a fixed attribution in case an information provider does not do so. It is necessary to ensure compliance with this attribution requirement.
- (2) The Use Case Partner should take measures to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of this data source. In particular, the likelihood that any data collected from this data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete (also in terms of representativeness of the target population), considering the goals of this scenario, must be carefully assessed. Any relevant reliability and accuracy concerns detected must be identified, and measures taken to address those concerns must be appropriately documented.

Given that the Use Case Partner is also responsible for the management of the data source, there are no applicable contractual or intellectual property-related restrictions applicable to the leveraging of this data source in the context of this scenario. Additionally, provided that only anonymous (e.g., aggregated) data are extracted from this data source, no relevant privacy / data protection issues arise in the context of this UC.

The status of implementation of requirements concerning UC #4, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 18](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario A, [Annex 19](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario B and [Annex 20](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario C to this Deliverable.

2.5.2 Privacy / Data Protection Compliance

2.5.2.1 UC #1: PARTICIPATORY POLICIES AGAINST RADICALIZATION

In the context of UC #1, Scenarios C and D raise potential privacy / data protection concerns, since the relevant data sources identified for these scenarios in D1.3 [5] (i.e., Dataset 4: Participatory policies against radicalisation in Twitter) strongly imply that the processing of personal data will be involved. For example, the collection and further processing of the following categories of personal data may be relevant to these Scenarios:

- (1) Names, surnames and/or pseudonyms (e.g., online handles);
- (2) Personal opinions posted on Twitter and – more generally – information publicly disclosed on Twitter (which may contain personal data);
- (3) Profiles created on Twitter users, based on information inferred from the automatic processing the above categories of personal data.

In this Section, we will present an overview of the main issues which the Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD user) – acting as a controller¹⁵, as it will leverage the PolicyCLOUD platform (and associated personal data processing activities) for its own specific purposes – must bear in mind when defining PolicyCLOUD platform use requirements in the context of these scenarios, with reference to the GDPR's data protection principles described in [Section 2.2.4](#) of D3.3 [1].

The status of implementation of privacy / data protection requirements concerning UC #1, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 5](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario A, [Annex 6](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario B, [Annex 7](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario C and [Annex 8](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario D to this Deliverable.

¹⁵ After completion of the PolicyCLOUD project, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s), on the other hand, will arguably act as a processor on behalf of the abovementioned controller, as the activities under the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s)'s responsibility will be limited to making personal data available for processing by the controller via the PolicyCLOUD platform, in strict compliance with the controller's instructions and specifications, for the specific purposes of the controller.

LAWFULNESS

As noted in D3.3 [1], any use of personal data must be performed based on consent provided by the data subjects, or otherwise on some other legitimate basis laid down in law, as set out in the GDPR or in other EU or Member State laws referred to by the GDPR.

Indeed, although personal data processed for these scenarios may be publicly available on Twitter, this does not exempt the Use Case Partner (or the intended PolicyCLOUD users) from the obligation to find a suitable legal basis for the processing of such data for its (their) own specific purposes. An assessment as to which of the legal bases afforded by the GDPR may be applicable and implementable in the context of these scenarios must therefore be carried out. This assessment must consider the full context of the scenarios, including the specific data sources to be used (e.g., the types of personal data included in those data sources, the way those data are collected – such as whether data are collected directly from data subjects, or indirectly from other data sources) and the specific goals to be reached through the scenarios.

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 4 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 4](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on the particularities of specific legal bases which may potentially be relevant for consideration.

2.5.2.1.1.1 CONSENT

Consent will only be a feasible legal basis for the processing of personal data on Twitter users where all the requirements laid out in [Section 2.2.4.1](#) of D3.3 [1] can be met in practice. Given the potential inherent imbalance of power between the intended PolicyCLOUD users for this use case (i.e., public authorities) and Twitter users (particularly if those users are citizens under a PolicyCLOUD user's jurisdiction), it must be made clear to social media users that they will suffer no adverse consequences if they choose not to provide their consent, or to later withdraw it.

Furthermore, reliance on consent implies the need to ensure that consent given can be withdrawn, at which point all processing of personal data related to the previously consenting Twitter users must cease¹⁶. In the absence of a legal basis to further process personal data collected on those users, it must then be deleted¹⁷. As such, consent can only be used where it is feasible to allow for the personal data of one or more social media users to be deleted and/or removed from further processing, should their consent be withdrawn.¹⁸

¹⁶Art. 7(3) GDPR.

¹⁷Art. 17(1)(b) GDPR.

¹⁸ On this point, as noted by Art. 11(2) GDPR, a controller is not required to comply with a data subject's request for the exercise of rights under the GDPR if it is no longer able to identify that data subject, except where that data subject provides additional information enabling their identification. This may be

In this particular context, consent of data subjects may be tricky to obtain, as the very nature of the collection and processing of personal data makes it difficult, if not impossible, for PolicyCLOUD users to interact directly with each specific data subject which may upload content to Twitter which is considered relevant by the PolicyCLOUD platform’s algorithms before the processing of such content is carried out, in order to request their consent for the processing of any of their personal data which may be collected. As such, other alternatives may need to be explored.

2.5.2.1.1.2 LEGITIMATE INTERESTS

As mentioned in D3.3 [1], it is key to note that Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR is not a legal basis which the GDPR affords to the processing of personal data carried out by public authorities in the performance of their tasks. As such, if a PolicyCLOUD user is acting as a public authority, in the performance of tasks mandated to it by law or regulation (as opposed to acting in the capacity of a private entity), this legal basis cannot be relied on by that user. To the extent that this is the case, this legal basis is not available in the context of this UC.

2.5.2.1.1.3 PUBLIC INTEREST

As mentioned in D3.3 [1], where it is not feasible for a PolicyCLOUD user to rely on either of the above options, that user may consider whether it can justify the intended processing of personal data on the need to perform a task carried out in the public interest, or in the exercise of official authority.¹⁹ As this legal basis presents the most flexible approach available to public authorities, when acting in the performance of their tasks, each user should assess whether the requirements described in D3.3 [1] for this legal basis are met, so as to ensure the lawfulness of the intended processing activities.

relevant in a scenario where a citizen’s personal data is promptly aggregated with that of other citizens, such that information pertaining to them is no longer linkable to them individually – in this case, it is reasonable to maintain that a withdrawal of consent would not prevent the controller from continuing to rely on the aggregated information for analytics purposes, insofar as it is not possible to establish a direct link between the aggregated information and the specific data subject. This would not apply, however, to any “raw” personal data kept on that data subject, which would be fully subject to their right to withdrawal of consent.

¹⁹ Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR.

LAWFULNESS (SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA)

As noted in D3.3 [1], where any special categories of personal data are to be collected and further processed, an applicable derogation to the GDPR's general prohibition on the processing of these personal data²⁰, from those listed in Art. 9(2) GDPR, or as may be further provided under applicable Member State law²¹, must also be identified. For clarity, to lawfully process special categories of personal data, the end-user must identify an applicable legal basis under Art. 6 GDPR and an applicable derogation under Art. 9 GDPR.

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 4 [5], further guidance to complement that of Section 4 of D3.3 [1] can be provided on the particularities of specific derogations which may potentially be relevant for consideration.

2.5.2.1.1.4 EXPLICIT CONSENT

On this point, we refer to the requirements set out in Section 2.2.4.2 and 2.2.4.1 of D3.3 [1], as all of those must be met to ensure validity of consent, and on the general observations as to the viability of reliance on consent for this use case made in Section 2.5.2.1.1.1 of this Deliverable.

2.5.2.1.1.5 DATA MANIFESTLY MADE PUBLIC BY THE DATA SUBJECT

As noted in Section 2.2.4.2 of D3.3 [1], where a data subject has manifestly made personal data public, this may serve as a derogation to the general prohibition on use of special categories of personal data related to them.²² This is a particularly relevant derogation for this UC, to the extent that personal data is to be collected from publicly available content uploaded on social media platforms. However, in this regard, the factors indicated by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), in the context of social media platforms, for determining whether this derogation is met are particularly relevant. The following points should be borne in mind:

- (1) If a social media platform's default settings, for the publication of content, are private, such that a data subject needs to actively choose to share data publicly, this weighs in favour of this derogation. As such, only data uploaded by social media users publicly (as opposed to data uploaded onto private profiles, groups, or shared through private direct messages, for example) should be considered in the context of this UC;
- (2) Where a social media platform is meant for the public disclosure of data in a non-intimate or personal setting, such as is the case with Twitter, this weighs in favour of this derogation;

²⁰ Established by Art. 9(1) GDPR.

²¹ In particular, regarding the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health, as set out in Art. 9(4) GDPR.

²² Art. 9(2)(e) GDPR.

- (3) If social media platforms inform their users that their content may be collected by other organisations, for purposes identical or similar to those pursued by the end-user, this weighs in favour of this derogation. Twitter's Privacy Policy [20] informs users that "*Twitter is public and Tweets are immediately viewable and searchable by anyone around the world*", and that they may "*share or disclose non-personal data, such as aggregated information like the total number of times people engaged with a Tweet, demographics, the number of people who clicked on a particular link or voted on a poll in a Tweet (even if only one did), the topics that people are Tweeting about in a particular location, some inferred interests, or reports to advertisers about how many people saw or clicked on their ads*". Each PolicyCLOUD user should make its own privacy policy publicly-available and easily accessible on its website(s) – as recommended in [Section 5.2.2.2](#) of D3.3 [1] (which is drafted in relation to UC #2, but can analogously be applied to this UC as well) – to further increase the likelihood of social media users becoming aware of how their data may be used.

Each PolicyCLOUD user should carefully assess whether this derogation may be applicable to any special categories of personal data (if any are collected) extracted from Twitter.

2.5.2.1.1.6 SUBSTANTIAL PUBLIC INTEREST

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.2](#) of D3.3 [1], this derogation requires a demonstrable need to process special categories of personal data to meet a substantial public interest with a basis in EU or Member State law applicable to the controller (i.e., the PolicyCLOUD user) which must:

- (1) Be proportionate to the interest pursued;
- (2) Respect the essence of the right to data protection.; and
- (3) Provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard data subjects' fundamental rights and interests.

Each PolicyCLOUD user should assess whether this derogation may be applicable, considering the purposes and goals relevant to this UC.

2.5.2.1.1.7 STATISTICAL PURPOSES

In light of the requirements explained in [Section 2.2.4.2](#) of D3.3 [1], as the processing of special categories of personal data, if relevant, may be carried out in this UC for statistical purposes, each PolicyCLOUD user should determine whether this processing can be based on EU or Member State law applicable to that user, which must:

- (1) Be proportionate to the interest pursued;
- (2) Respect the essence of the right to data protection; and
- (3) Provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard data subjects' fundamental rights and interests.

Where this is the case, this derogation may be applicable, provided that the processing carried out by the relevant PolicyCLOUD user via the platform is supported by specific safeguards, as specified in Art. 89(1) GDPR and further described in [Section 2.2.4.2](#) of D3.3 [1]. In order to provide assurances that this derogation may be applicable to the relevant PolicyCLOUD users, the Use Case Partner and the Consortium must collaborate to ensure that such safeguards are adequately implemented on the PolicyCLOUD platform.

FAIRNESS

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.3](#) of D3.3 [1], for the processing of personal data to be considered as fair under the GDPR, the controller must ensure that personal data are handled in ways that may be reasonably expected by data subjects, and must not use such data in a way that may produce unjustified adverse effects on them.

Considering Dataset 4 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 4](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on specific key elements to be considered by the Use Case Partner, under the principle of fairness.

2.5.2.1.1.8 INTERACTION

Given that PolicyCLOUD platform will be collecting data indirectly from Twitter, this requires the relevant PolicyCLOUD user to have channels in place through which data subjects can communicate with them, including to exercise their rights as data subjects (under the GDPR and local laws). As noted under the principle of transparency, addressed in [Section 2.2.4.4](#) of D3.3 [1], this also requires the user to take reasonable steps towards ensuring that data subjects are aware that their personal data may be processed in the manner intended by this UC – such as by publishing information on these activities on a publicly available website managed by the user.

2.5.2.1.1.9 EXPECTATION

This element is particularly important in this UC, as depending on what personal data about the data subjects is made available to the relevant PolicyCLOUD user for processing via the platform, and the subsequent processing actions which the user may perform on those data, the fairness of such processing may be called into question (due to being reasonably unexpected by the relevant data subjects) pursuant to the GDPR. In particular, while it may be argued that the collection of data subjects' publicly available comments, posts, and interactions on Twitter and their subsequent aggregation in order to provide relevant statistics, trends, charts, etc., may, to some extent, be expected by data subjects when they publicly post or comment on Twitter (or, at least, could arguably be seen as not excessively intrusive), the same is arguably not the case if the PolicyCLOUD platform were to, e.g., allow for the storage of data subjects' opinions (posted on social media) in such a way that allows the PolicyCLOUD user to directly identify data subjects, trace content back to its original source (e.g., through a hyperlink) and directly interact with those data subjects. This level of intrusiveness may potentially be considered as excessive and, as such, run afoul of this principle. It should further be noted that such an activity could also be considered as out-of-scope in the context of the policy-making purposes for which the

PolicyCLOUD platform is being developed. As such, it is strongly recommended that each relevant PolicyCLOUD user consider, whenever possible, the aggregation of personal data collected from public sources, to mitigate the risk of unfair processing.

One possible exception which could be borne in mind would be the case of processing unaggregated personal data on social media influencers. The inherent role played by influencers (which involves a greater deal of public exposure) suggests that they may have a lessened expectation of privacy regarding content which they make publicly available on social networks, such that the processing of such content by a PolicyCLOUD users for the purposes pursued in this UC would not be an unreasonable violation of their expectations. This should be carefully assessed by each relevant PolicyCLOUD user when identifying the legal basis (or bases) applicable to them (e.g., in the Legitimate Interests Assessment [LIA] performed, where feasible, or in the assessment as to whether such an activity may be considered as performed in pursuit of a task in the public interest).

2.5.2.1.1.10 NON-DISCRIMINATION

Personal data should not be collected on social media users for the purpose of discriminating against them (such as to cause harm or detriment to social media users publishing content seen as problematic by the end-user), nor should this be the end-result of policies developed using social media users' personal data.

TRANSPARENCY

To ensure compliance with the principle of transparency, as described in [Section 2.2.4.4](#) of D3.3 [1], each relevant PolicyCLOUD user must ensure that it provides complete and understandable information to the relevant data subjects on their data processing practices.

Ideally, this would involve the development of an information notice to be provided directly to social media users upon collection of their personal data, in writing. However, given that personal data is not collected directly from data subjects in this UC (but rather indirectly, from Twitter), PolicyCLOUD users may be able to argue for the exemption provided under Art. 14(5)(b) GDPR, where the provision of information directly to each individual social media user proves impossible or would represent a disproportionate effort for those PolicyCLOUD users. [21] Each PolicyCLOUD user should develop a specific assessment to demonstrate that this exception is applicable, contrasting the effort required of the PolicyCLOUD user to ensure that each individual social media user would receive information directly against the harm which may arise for social media users should they not have any access to such information (e.g., should they not become aware of the processing carried out by the PolicyCLOUD user). This can be carried out as part of a broader data protection impact assessment. Where the effort required of a PolicyCLOUD user would be clearly disproportionate considering the (low) impact upon data subjects, this exemption can be relied on.

Where this exemption applies, PolicyCLOUD users must take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of social media users in spite of the fact that this information is

not directly provided to them, such as by displaying the information on a publicly available website, as stated in Art. 14(5)(b) GDPR. Any information notice or privacy policy developed (e.g., to be made available on a website managed by a PolicyCLOUD user, as seen above) must bear in mind the inherent tension between the GDPR requirements of providing comprehensive information, and ensuring that the information provided is concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible in mind – this requires an assessment as to which information should be prioritised, what the appropriate level of detail is and which are the best means by which to convey this information to data subjects. [21] Whenever feasible, PolicyCLOUD users should rely on the so-called “layered approach”, allowing them to structure the information into relevant categories which the data subject can select, to ensure immediate access to the information deemed most relevant by the data subject and prevent information fatigue. [21] [22]

Whenever personal data is lawfully processed by PolicyCLOUD users for further purpose(s) (i.e., where these further purpose(s) are compatible with the original, or where an additional legal basis exists for the further purpose(s)), the information made available on the end-user’s website must be promptly updated regarding such further purpose(s), under Art. 14(4) GDPR.

PURPOSE LIMITATION

As seen in [Section 2.2.4.5](#) of D3.3 [1], to ensure compliance with the principle of purpose limitation, under Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, PolicyCLOUD users must identify specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes for which personal data are to be collected and processed via the platform, and then refrain from using personal data for any other incompatible purpose. Through the presumption established for “*further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes*” in Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, provided that the safeguards of Art. 89(1) GDPR are respected, it is arguably possible for users to make further use of personal data collected in a commercial context (such as in the context of social media platforms) for statistical analysis aimed at the pursuit of a public interest.

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 4 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 4](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on specific key elements to be considered by the Use Case Partner, under the principle of purpose limitation.

2.5.2.1.1.11 SPECIFICITY

The specific purposes for which the PolicyCLOUD user intends to process data collected from social media platforms should be made clear in the user’s publicly available information notice, as mentioned in [Section 2.2.4.5](#) of D3.3 [1].

2.5.2.1.1.12 NECESSITY

The PolicyCLOUD user should carefully assess whether the purposes for which it intends to use the platform can be met by using only anonymous or aggregated social media data (preferred approach), as opposed to identifiable data (e.g., posts or content linked to a specific social media user through a name or social media handle, or through other identifiers).

2.5.2.1.1.13 COMPATIBILITY

The presumption of compatibility mentioned above arguably applies to this UC, for research and statistical purposes.

2.5.2.1.1.14 LIMITATIONS TO FURTHER PROCESSING

The point raised in [Section 2.5.2.1.1.9](#) of this Deliverable on tracking or targeting of specific social media users is relevant for this element also.

DATA MINIMISATION

As seen in [Section 2.2.4.6](#) of D3.3 [1], compliance with the principle of data minimisation requires a minimalistic approach to personal data, in the sense that:

- (1) As little of it as possible should be processed to meet an intended purpose;
- (2) Only personal data which are adequate, relevant, and strictly necessary to meet a purpose should be used;
- (3) If a purpose can be met without using personal data (e.g., using only anonymous or aggregated data), then no personal data should be used at all.

Considering Dataset 4 [5], aside from the general guidance provided in [Section 2.2.4.6](#) of D3.3 [1], the Use Case Partner should arguably assess, for example, whether there is any added value in retaining the ability to identify specific users uploading content onto Twitter for the policy-making purposes which are pursued by this UC. If so, the Use Case Partner should then consider whether preserving this added value serves a legitimate goal, if the added value is substantial, and if the benefits of retaining this ability outweigh the potential impact on the social media users in question. If the Use Case Partner determines that the use of personal data, preserving a link to the identity of individual social media users, is necessary, then the Use Case Partner must be able to demonstrate that each data point collected is specifically relevant to the purpose pursued. Any irrelevant personal data will be deemed as excessive and should not be collected or further processed.

ACCURACY

Ensuring accuracy of data used is fundamental from the legal perspective – as seen in [Section 2.2.4.7](#) of D3.3 [1] – but also from the ethical perspective, given that inaccurate, incomplete, misleading or biased data can result in erroneous outputs, culminating in misguided policy-making with a potential impact at an individual and societal level – as seen in [Sections 2.1.3 and 2.1.4](#) of D3.3 [1].

Given that data will be extracted directly from Twitter, the principle of accuracy will generally be met in the sense that it should be easy to objectively demonstrate that a given Twitter user or individual factually uploaded a given piece of content; however, the more subjective analysis of ensuring the accuracy of data or information contained within uploaded content (and of the opinions or sentiments which can be derived from such content via the platform) is another matter.

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 4 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 4](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on specific key elements to be considered by Use Case Partner, under the principle of accuracy.

2.5.2.1.1.15 DATA SOURCE RELIABILITY

Where social media platforms are concerned, reliability of content uploaded will always be a relevant risk to be mitigated (as those platforms generally do not exercise any editorial powers over the content uploaded by social media users). The Use Case Partner, in collaboration with the Consortium, must identify measures to mitigate the risk of reliance on false or misleading data, to the extent that this may affect the outcome of the policy-making process.

2.5.2.1.1.16 VERIFICATION

Given that this use case will rely on several streaming data sources, a continuous effort to ensure accuracy will need to be carried out, namely by overwriting older data with newer data, to prevent excessive data aging, through specific and adequate “rollover” periods to be determined by the Use Case Partner.

2.5.2.1.1.17 UPDATED DATA

As noted above, whenever a streaming data source is used – which is the case for Twitter – appropriate rollover periods (i.e., periods after which older data is to be overwritten by newer data collected) should be defined.

STORAGE LIMITATION

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.8](#) of D3.3 [1], this principle becomes practically relevant whenever personal data is collected, if it is not promptly anonymised or aggregated (with the underlying raw data being deleted as soon as possible). Noting that personal data avoidance is the preferred approach under the data minimisation principle, whenever this is not feasible, then the relevant PolicyCLOUD user should define specific retention periods for the personal data collected, based on the strict minimum period for which retention of those data is needed to ensure that the purpose for their collection and processing can be met.

Considering Dataset 4 [5], aside from the general guidance provided in [Section 2.2.4.8](#) of D3.3 [1], the Use Case Partner should consider that, when dealing with streaming data sources, it is important for the PolicyCLOUD users to be able to define an appropriate retention and/or overwrite period to avoid data aging (i.e., defining a short “rollover” period after which older data will be overwritten by newer data collected through the stream). The platform should allow its users to define retention periods and include tools for automatic deletion or aggregation of underlying data after a user-defined retention period is exceeded.

2.5.2.2 UC #2: INTELLIGENT POLICIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRI-FOOD INDUSTRY

In this Section, we will present an overview of the main issues which the Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD user) – acting as a controller – must bear in mind when defining PolicyCLOUD platform use requirements in the context of UC #2, with reference to the GDPR's data protection principles described in [Section 2.2.4](#) of D3.3 [1].

Of the different data sources indicated for this UC [5], it seems that the following present a clearer potential for capturing personal data:

- (1) Dataset 12: Wine varieties and brands information from Twitter;
- (2) Dataset 13: Wine varieties and brands information from Facebook;
- (3) Dataset 14: Wine varieties and brands information from Instagram;
- (4) Dataset 15: Wine varieties and brands information from LinkedIn.

As such, this Section will, in principle, be more relevant to those specific data sources (but should also be considered for the other data sources, if use of any of the other data sources also implies a collection of personal data).

It should first be noted that this specific UC [4] may entail the collection and further processing of various categories of personal data, such as:

- (1) Names, surnames and/or pseudonyms (e.g., online handles);
- (2) Personal opinions posted on social media platforms and – more generally – information publicly disclosed on those platforms (which may contain personal data);
- (3) Profiles created on social media users, based on information inferred from the automatic processing of the above categories of personal data.

For the purposes of this UC, the Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD user) shall be considered as an (independent) controller within the meaning of the GDPR, as it will use personal data available through the features of the PolicyCLOUD platform for their own specific purposes.

Given that the datasets relevant to this UC which may contain personal data are comparable to the dataset relevant to UC #1 which may contain personal data (as all such datasets refer to information extracted from social media platforms), the considerations drawn in [Section 2.5.2.1](#) of this Deliverable may be extended to UC #2, with the necessary adaptations considering that, in UC #2, more social media platforms than just Twitter are considered, and with the below specifications.

The status of implementation of privacy / data protection requirements concerning UC #2, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 9](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario A [Annex 10](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario B and [Annex 11](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario C to this Deliverable.

LAWFULNESS

2.5.2.2.1.1 LEGITIMATE INTERESTS

It is not entirely clear whether the Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD users), in leveraging the PolicyCLOUD platform, may be considered as acting as a public authority in the performance of tasks mandated to it by law or regulation (as opposed to acting in the capacity of a private entity). If this is not the case, and they may instead be seen as operating as if they were a private entity, the legal basis afforded by Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR will be available.

Where Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR is available, each PolicyCLOUD user will need to perform an LIA, following the practical steps described in [Section 2.2.4.1](#) of D3.3 [1]. This can be carried out as part of a broader data protection impact assessment. Where the interests of the user clearly outweigh the impact upon data subjects or can otherwise be supported by additional safeguards to mitigate the impact upon data subjects to an acceptable degree, this legal basis can be relied on.

LAWFULNESS (SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA)

2.5.2.2.1.2 DATA MANIFESTLY MADE PUBLIC BY THE DATA SUBJECT

The Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD users) should carefully assess whether this derogation may be applicable to any special categories of personal data (if any are collected) extracted from Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, or any other data sources it wishes to rely on.

PURPOSE LIMITATION

2.5.2.2.1.3 COMPATIBILITY

The presumption of compatibility mentioned above arguably applies here, for research and statistical purposes. However, taking into account the general scope of the PolicyCLOUD platform and the purposes/goals of this UC, the Use Case Partner (or intended PolicyCLOUD users) should generally refrain from further processing personal data to track or target specific social media users and directly interact with them on social media platforms, as this purpose may arguably be considered as excessive and unlawful (thereby incompatible with the other purposes for which the Use Case Partner, or intended PolicyCLOUD users, may wish to use those data), as specified under [Section 2.5.2.1.1.9](#) of this Deliverable.

2.5.2.3 UC #3: FACILITATING URBAN POLICY MAKING AND MONITORING THROUGH CROWDSOURCING DATA ANALYSIS

Of the two data sources indicated as relevant for UC #3 in D1.3 [5], the only one to present a clear potential for capturing personal data is Dataset 18 (Sofia Municipality Signals), i.e., signals from citizens, coming through the contact centre of the municipality. In this Section, we will present an overview of the main issues which the Use Case Partner – acting as a controller – must bear in mind when defining PolicyCLOUD platform use requirements in the context of the use of Dataset 18, with reference to the GDPR's data protection principles described in [Section 2.2.4](#) of D3.3 [1].

The status of implementation of privacy / data protection requirements concerning UC #3, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 12](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 1, [Annex 13](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 2 [Annex 14](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 3 [Annex 15](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 4 [Annex 16](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 5 and [Annex 17](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 6 to this Deliverable.

LAWFULNESS

In light of the requirements explained in [Section 6.3.2](#) of D3.3 [1], the processing of special categories of personal data is carried out in UC #3 for statistical purposes and according with Art. 25m of the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act, which states that "*Personal data originally collected for a different purpose may be processed for the purposes of the National Archive Funds, for scientific, for historical research or for statistical purposes. In such cases, the controller shall apply appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject in accordance with Article 89 (1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.*".

FAIRNESS

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.3](#) of D3.3 [1], for the processing under this UC to be considered as fair under the GDPR, the Use Case Partner must ensure that personal data are handled in ways that may be reasonably expected by data subjects and not use such data in a way that may produce unjustified adverse effects on them.

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 18 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 6.3.3](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on specific key elements to be considered by the Use Case Partner, under the principle of fairness.

2.5.2.3.1.1 EXPECTATION

If data subjects are led to believe that personal data collected on them will be used to improve the municipality's policy-making abilities, this should be the only objective pursued with those personal data – using them to profile and target individuals raising problematic complaints, or for other unrelated and arguably illegitimate purposes (e.g., sending of marketing communications), must be strictly avoided. This will imply controls around purpose limitation, including access control.

2.5.2.3.1.2 NON-DISCRIMINATION

The Use Case Partner must not discriminate against data subjects. In particular, personal data should not be collected on citizens for the purpose of discriminating against them (such as to cause harm or detriment to citizens filing larger numbers of complaints), nor should this be the end-result of policies developed using citizens' personal data – this requirement is strongly tied to applicable ethical

considerations of avoidance of bias and non-discrimination, as seen in [Sections 2.1.3 and 2.1.4](#) of D3.3 [1].

2.5.2.3.1.3 POWER BALANCE

Asymmetric power balances shall be avoided or mitigated when possible. The Use Case Partner must ensure that it complies with all applicable legal obligations when handling citizens' personal data and must develop policies based on those data with a reasoned and critical approach, having citizens' fundamental rights and freedoms at the forefront of the decision-making process, to avoid abuse of power or arbitrariness.

TRANSPARENCY

To ensure its compliance with the principle of transparency, as seen in [Section 2.2.4.4](#) of D3.3 [1], the Use Case Partner must ensure that it provides complete and understandable information to data subjects on its data processing practices.

Ideally, this would involve the development of an information notice, to be provided directly to citizens upon collection of their personal data, in writing. The Use Case Partner must develop such a notice with the inherent tension between the GDPR requirements of providing comprehensive information, and ensuring that the information provided is concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible in mind – this requires an assessment as to which information should be prioritised, what the appropriate level of detail is, and which are the best means by which to convey this information to data subjects. [21] Whenever feasible, the Use Case Partner should rely on the so-called 'layered approach', allowing them to structure the information into relevant categories which the data subject can select, to ensure immediate access to the information deemed most relevant by the data subject and prevent information fatigue. [21] [22] Where information is collected outside of an online context, one way to follow this approach would be to provide citizens with an abbreviated paper-based notice at the municipality's contact centre, including a link to the more complete privacy statement made available online. [21]

Any material or substantive changes to information notices, reflecting changes to the underlying processing activities, should be communicated directly to citizens in a manner which ensures that they will be noticed. [21] It will not be valid to merely inform data subjects that they should regularly contact the municipality or check an online information notice for changes or updates, given the inherent unfairness to data subjects which this represents. [21]

Therefore, with regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: *"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the*

processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."

PURPOSE LIMITATION

As noted in [Section 2.2.4.5](#) of D3.3 [1], to ensure compliance with the principle of purpose limitation, under Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, the Use Case Partner must identify specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes for which personal data are to be collected and processed, and then refrain from using personal data for any other incompatible purpose. Through the presumption established for "*further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes*" in Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, provided that the safeguards of Art. 89(1) GDPR are respected, it is arguably possible for the Use Case Partner to make further use of personal data collected in the context of the municipality contact centre to be further used for statistical analysis aimed at the pursuit of a public interest [24].

To this end, considering the characteristics of Dataset 18 [5], further guidance to complement that of [Section 6.3.5](#) of D3.3 [1] can be provided on specific key elements to be considered by the Use Case Partner, under the principle of purpose limitation.

2.5.2.3.1.4 SPECIFICITY

The purposes must be specific to the processing; it should be made explicitly clear to citizens why their personal data is being processed, in the context of this UC.

2.5.2.3.1.5 NECESSITY

The Use Case Partner should carefully assess whether the purposes for which it intends to use the PolicyCLOUD platform can be met with only anonymous or aggregated data collected from signals and/or complaints (preferred approach), as opposed to identifiable data (e.g., specific signals/complaints linked to a specific citizen through a name or national identification number, or through other identifiers).

2.5.2.3.1.6 COMPATIBILITY

The presumption of compatibility mentioned above applies to this UC, for research and statistical purposes.

DATA MINIMISATION

Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via the PolicyCLOUD platform. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the Use Case Partner has noted that no text analysis is intended

to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].

2.5.2.4 UC #4: PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS TOWARDS UNEMPLOYMENT RISKS IDENTIFICATION AND POLICY MAKING

The main and only dataset envisaged for UC #4 identified in D1.3 [5] is Dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count), retrieved from the Open Data Camden platform, which allows the general public, researchers and developers to access, analyse and share information about the Camden Borough. [17] According to the information made available by the Use Case Partner, this dataset does not contain any personal data, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden Borough) [3].

However, to comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to citizens to which the data included on the Open Data Camden platform refers should be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: *"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."*

The status of implementation of privacy / data protection requirements concerning UC #4, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the relevant **Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists** – see [Annex 18](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario A, [Annex 19](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario B and [Annex 20](#) – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario C to this Deliverable.

3 Additional Identified Requirements

3.1 Cloud Infrastructure Utilization & Data Governance (WP3)

In this Section, legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements applicable to PolicyCLOUD project components under the purview of WP3 which were not developed (or not fully developed) as of the date of submission of D3.3 – in particular, the Interim Repository and Incentives Management components – will be addressed.

3.1.1 Interim Repository

As described in [Sections 3 and 6.4.3](#) of D6.6 [34], to facilitate registration management of the heterogeneous data sources which may be leveraged via the PolicyCLOUD platform in connection with the PolicyCLOUD project (which could otherwise imply setting up a potentially high number of different adaptors in connection with the platform's gateway), the Consortium has decided to set up an interim data repository on the platform, aptly called the Interim Repository. This repository will further enable the assessment of each data source relevant to the project in terms of its compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements (further addressed in [Sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2](#) of this Deliverable), before each data source is uploaded onto the Interim Repository, and before each data source is subsequently uploaded onto the main PolicyCLOUD data repository. This further allows the specific technical / Use Case Partners relevant to each data source to carry out a more detailed discussion and collaboration on relevant action points related to those data sources.

Given that, according to the information provided by the Consortium, the Interim Repository will be hosted on the same cloud-based infrastructure which supports the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform, the same requirements described in [Section 2.2](#) of this Deliverable apply in full to the Interim Repository. In particular:

- It should be ensured that the conditions established in the framework in place with the cloud-based infrastructure provider (through the combination of the relevant SLA [26] and OLA [27]) apply in full to the Interim Repository – in other words, that the terms applicable to the providers' services relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project fully apply to the Interim Repository. Where this is not the case, those terms must be amended to ensure this. This should also be considered in connection with the full assessment and consolidation of the contents of EGI.eu's template DPA with EGI Foundation as a Processor relevant to Cloud Compute services [29] – see [Section 2.2.1](#) of this Deliverable;
- The potential additional impact on environmental sustainability which leveraging the provider's cloud-based infrastructure to host the Interim Repository (as opposed to relying on local infrastructure and/or storage capabilities) should be reduced to a minimum, assuming that the

choice to rely on such a cloud-based infrastructure is more technically efficient than non-cloud-based alternatives – see [Section 2.2.2](#) of this Deliverable;

- A dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis (but also from use of a cloud-based infrastructure, in general) should be carried out regarding the Interim Repository, so as to define and implement adequate technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of data stored in the Interim Repository. This should also include specific restrictions on the unlawful reuse of personal data – in particular, it should be ensured that the PolicyCLOUD platform’s Data Governance and Privacy Enforcement mechanism (better described in [Section 6.3](#) of D3.4 [28]) is applicable also to the Interim Repository – see [Section 2.2.3](#), and also [Section 2.1.1](#), of this Deliverable;
- Technical and/or organisational measures must be implemented to ensure that the Interim Repository allows for the exercise of Data Subject Rights – at a minimum, the Interim Repository should not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights. This applies not only to the rights of [users of the PolicyCLOUD platform](#), but also of [individuals whose personal data may be contained in data sources processed via the Interim Repository](#) – see [Section 2.2.4](#), and also [Section 2.3.4](#), of this Deliverable;
- Technical and/or organisational measures must be implemented to ensure that personal data is not stored in the Interim Repository for any longer than necessary to allow for the data source within which it is contained to be assessed and prepared for ingestion in the PolicyCLOUD data repository. In particular, it should be ensured that, once the data source is transitioned from the Interim Repository to the PolicyCLOUD data repository, all data pertaining to that data source is irreversibly deleted from the Interim Repository (or otherwise irreversibly anonymised, such as through aggregation) – see [Section 2.2.5](#) and also [Section 2.1.2](#) of this Deliverable.

The status of implementation of the requirements concerning the Interim Repository, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

3.1.2 Incentives Management

As described in [Section 5](#) of D3.4 [28], the PolicyCLOUD platform will include a tool to identify, declare and manage incentives (including social, cultural and political incentives, among others, depending on the goals set by PolicyCLOUD users and the relevant audience) for citizens' engagement, based on the idea that including citizens as participants in the policy development and management process enhances the acceptability of, and confidence in, created policies – the Incentives Management tool. This tool is meant as a tracking/management tool for the different incentives, motivations and actions defined by users, without collecting or processing any information about the individuals (e.g., citizens) targeted by such incentives. The more low-level, specific management of incentives and motivations will need to be handled by users outside of the scope of the PolicyCLOUD platform (e.g., through ad-hoc crowdsourcing platforms which best suit the user's needs. This tool will be integrated in the PDT, to afford users a single interface from which they can manage both the PDT and Incentives Management functionalities of the platform.

3.1.2.1 PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION

Given that the Incentives Management tool is not aimed at collecting or processing any information about the individuals targeted by the incentives managed through the tool, it appears that no personal data on such individuals will be processed in connection with this tool. As a result, no relevant privacy/data protection concerns are triggered, insofar as those individuals are concerned.

It is, however, assumed that personal data on PolicyCLOUD users making use of the tool may be processed (e.g., to allow users to access the tool via registered accounts on the PolicyCLOUD platform, to contact users with relevant service updates or other communications, to address requests or questions raised by users). Where this is confirmed, similar requirements as defined for the PDT in [Section 3.3](#) of D3.3 [1] apply to this tool. In particular:

1. *Lawfulness*. An appropriate legal basis for each purpose for which personal data on tool users may be collected should be identified, under Art. 6 GDPR. All steps needed to properly implement the identified legal bases should be taken – this will depend on the legal bases selected, which in turn depends on the manner in which user personal data may be processed via the tool;²³
2. *Fairness*. Personal data on tool users should not be used in a manner which may violate their reasonable expectations. Profiling tool users or covertly sharing their data with third parties for marketing purposes may qualify as unfair processing of personal data, in particular if this is not transparently disclosed to users. There should also be mechanisms in place to ensure that users are able to exercise their rights in relation to any personal data of theirs which may be collected during the use of the platform;

²³ As this is further specified during the Project, this Section will be updated accordingly.

3. *Transparency*. A specific privacy policy should be developed for the tool, in order to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the tool in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all of the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR. To the extent that cookies or similar tracking technologies are to be used on the platform, this should be clearly disclosed to users in the privacy policy, as well as in a separate cookie banner presented to users upon accessing the tool, offering users relevant choices as to their cookie preferences. Given that the tool will be integrated into a single user interface alongside the PDT, this requirement may be more practically addressed by revising the PDT's Privacy Policy, to ensure that it appropriately reflects the processing activities which may be carried out on tool users;
4. *Purpose limitation*. Personal data collected on tool users should not be used for purposes which are incompatible with those declared in the privacy policy;
5. *Data minimisation*. Only the strict minimum amount of user personal data needed to properly provide the tool's functionalities, to perform any supporting functions, or for any other purpose for which a legal basis can be identified, should be collected;
6. *Accuracy*. Users should be given the possibility to rectify any personal data they submit, or which is collected on them, in connection with use of the tool. This is linked to the principle of fairness, described above.
7. *Storage limitation*. Personal data on tool users may only be stored for the strict minimum amount of time needed to meet any of the purposes for which they were lawfully collected, after which the personal data should be irreversibly anonymised or deleted. This will require the identification of appropriate retention periods for any such personal data collected. Data retention concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to this tool – are more generally covered in [Section 2.1.2](#) of this Deliverable.
8. *Security*. Appropriate security measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of any collected and further stored personal data, as well as the resilience of systems used to collect and further store those data, must be implemented. Data security concerns related to the PolicyCLOUD project – including those relevant to this tool – are more generally covered in [Section 2.1.1](#) of this Deliverable.
9. *Accountability*. Records of evidence showing compliance with these requirements must be kept.

The status of implementation of privacy / data protection requirements concerning the Incentives Management tool, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

3.1.2.2 TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Just as noted regarding the PDT in [Section 3.3](#) of D3.3 [1], it is important to define terms and conditions for the use of the Incentives Management tool, so as to properly regulate the service relationship established between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and tool users (i.e., individual users, or organisations to which the individual users belong). These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for the use of the tool to be allowed. The matters which should be regulated, with the necessary adaptations, include those described in [Section 2.4.1](#) of this Deliverable.

Given that the tool will be integrated into a single user interface alongside the PDT, this requirement may be more practically addressed by ensuring that the terms and conditions to be developed for the PDT (see [Section 2.4](#) of this Deliverable) reflect appropriate use terms for the tool as well.

The status of implementation of terms and conditions concerning the Incentives Management tool, as of the date of this Deliverable, as well as the next steps towards implementation of any missing requirements, is reported in the **Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 2](#) – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

3.2 Communication, Exploitation, Standardisation, Roadmapping & Business Development (WP7)

3.2.1 Data Marketplace

The main idea behind the PolicyCLOUD platform's Data Marketplace component is to create a community of users who will be able, through this component, to provide and share various assets related to the PolicyCLOUD platform's scope. This component also aims at being one of the PolicyCLOUD project's main ambassadors to different external communities (third parties), by disseminating and demonstrating the main outcomes of the project. To this end, this component should provide PolicyCLOUD users with means for storing and retrieving (after searching) several types of assets. In summary, the Data Marketplace will consist of a public web-based environment with many different APIs and functionalities, to cover all the different requirements of the project's stakeholders. [25]

The scope of the Data Marketplace, in relation to the other components of the PolicyCLOUD platform (such as the PDT/PME, or the pre-existing analytics tools) is different and unique. More specifically, the Data Marketplace is intended to offer PolicyCLOUD users ready-to-use sets of solutions related to various subjects. At the same time, it will enable users to upload different types of assets that may be leveraged by any other users to solve and/or handle their specific needs. In the current implementation of the Data Marketplace, all uploaded assets will be made available to all users; however, at a subsequent stage of development, users uploading assets to the platform will be able to set limitations on the types or identities of users to which such assets may be made available. [25]

PolicyCLOUD users' motivations to use the Data Marketplace may include the need to search for and retrieve assets to help them either resolve certain business issues, achieve certain educational goals, or even for personal reasons. [25]

Ultimately, the Data Marketplace is designed as a smart, user-based asset repository. PolicyCLOUD users will be able to use this component to share ready-to-use solutions and/or tools (including, e.g., data sources, analytics tools, policy models) with other users. [25]

The main legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements identified for the Data Marketplace component are as follows:

- (1) The Data Marketplace should incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats;
- (2) Should personal data be included in data sources made available through the Data Marketplace, the PolicyCLOUD users uploading such data sources to the Data Marketplace, the users accessing such data sources and/or the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) must identify appropriate legal bases under the GDPR (and implement all associated compliance steps) to ensure that this making available of personal data can be lawfully carried out, and that the relevant data sources can be lawfully leveraged by accessing users;
- (3) All potential controllers involved in the uploading and accessing of data sources containing personal data via the Data Marketplace (i.e., uploading and accessing PolicyCLOUD users, the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s)) should be clear and honest with the relevant data subjects about their identities, the methods they will use to process personal data, and the purposes for which they are to process those personal data;
- (4) Terms and conditions for the use of the Data Marketplace should be defined, to properly regulate the service relationship established between the PolicyCLOUD Manager(s) and PolicyCLOUD users. These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for use of the Data Marketplace to be allowed;
- (5) A due diligence exercise must be performed, and a compliance declaration obtained from PolicyCLOUD users uploading assets to the Data Marketplace, with regards to the compliance of those assets with applicable legal/regulatory and ethical/societal requirements.

However, as the definition of requirements for the Data Marketplace component of the platform is still ongoing, other specific requirements which may be raised will be addressed in the coming months, with a final progress report as to their identification and implementation to be reported in the last update to this Deliverable (D3.9). The current requirements identified, as of the date of this Deliverable, are reported in the **WP7 Legal/Ethical Checklist** – see [Annex 21](#) – WP7 Legal/Ethical Checklist to this Deliverable.

4 Conclusion and Next Steps

In this Deliverable, an update on the implementation of relevant legal/regulatory and ethical/societal concerns requirements previously identified as applicable to the PolicyCLOUD platform was presented in [Section 2](#). This Deliverable further sought to identify additional requirements for components which either did not exist, or were not fully developed, as of the date of submission of D3.3 [1], which thus represent brand-new requirements applicable to the PolicyCLOUD platform in [Section 3](#). Finally, in [Annexes 1 to 21](#), new and updated **Legal/Ethical Checklists** for each PolicyCLOUD project WP, containing a consolidated set of legal/ethical requirements and details on the current status of their implementation, were provided, as tools to track the completion of any missing implementation actions in the final year of the project.

Concerning legal/regulatory concerns and requirements, the focus was kept, for practicality and to assure that requirements could be defined in a PolicyCLOUD user-agnostic manner, on the EU legal/regulatory framework (as opposed to local laws applicable in specific Member States or third countries).

As of the date of this Deliverable, several PolicyCLOUD platform components are still under development (e.g., Data Marketplace). The four UCs also continue to be refined, with UC Partners defining further relevant data sources and scenarios. As such, all issues and requirements reflected in this Deliverable were provided based on the current state of the PolicyCLOUD project as of the date of the submission of this Deliverable, and may be subject to further consolidation in the final year of the project.

In the foreseen update to this Deliverable (D3.9), due in October 2022 (M34), an updated and final implementation report will be provided, not only duly reflecting all relevant developments occurring in the PolicyCLOUD project from the date of submission of this Deliverable to the project's end, but also providing a final set of requirements which are understood and accepted by the Consortium as vital to ensure the ethical and legal soundness of the Project, as well as a description of the specific measures taken to address each requirement.

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Annex 1 – WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist

WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist, as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Description
1	An information security management system (ISMS), covering at least the operational units, locations and processes for providing the PolicyCLOUD platform, must be defined, implemented, maintained and continually improved.
2	A risk assessment about the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks on roles or individuals, regarding the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform must be carried out. This risk assessment must cover at least the following areas, insofar as these are applicable to the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform and are in the area of responsibility of the Consortium: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations; • Development, testing and release of changes; and • Operation of the system components.
3	The mitigating measures defined in the risk assessment must be implemented, privileging separation of duties, unless impossible for organisational or technical reasons, in which case the measures shall include the monitoring of activities in order to detect unauthorised or unintended changes as well as misuse and the subsequent appropriate actions.
4	Information security requirements/considerations must be included in the management of the PolicyCLOUD Project.
5	Risk assessments must be carried out on the entire perimeter of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
6	The results of risk assessments must be made available to relevant stakeholders.
7	Risk assessments must be revised at least after each major change that may affect the security of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
8	Risks must be prioritized according to their criticality.
9	A plan must be implemented to treat risks according to their priority level by reducing or avoiding them through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them, so that each risk level is reduced to a threshold which the risk owner(s) deems acceptable (Residual Risk).
10	The risk treatment plan must be made available to relevant stakeholders.
11	If PolicyCLOUD users will share risks, the shared risks must be associated to Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs) and described in the user documentation.
12	The risk treatment plan must be revised every time risk assessments are revised.
13	Information security-sensitive positions relevant to the PolicyCLOUD Project must be classified according to their level of risk, including positions related to IT administration and to the provisioning of the cloud service in the production environment, and all positions with access to data or system components.
14	Each Partner must include in its employment contracts or on a dedicated code of conduct or ethics an overarching agreement from internal and external employees to act ethically in their professional duties.
15	Each Partner must ensure that all internal and external employees are required by their employment terms and conditions to comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures.

Control No.	Description
16	Each Partner must ensure that the employment terms for all internal and external employees include a non-disclosure provision, which shall cover any information that has been obtained or generated as part of the PolicyCLOUD Project, even if anonymised and decontextualized.
17	Each Partner must ensure that all employees have completed a relevant security awareness and training program defined for them.
18	Each Partner must apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of internal and external employees if their employment is terminated or changed (e.g., where the employee no longer works with the PolicyCLOUD Project).
19	Each Partner must ensure that non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements are agreed with internal employees, external service providers and suppliers.
20	An inventory of assets must be maintained. For each asset, the information needed to apply the PolicyCLOUD Project's risk management procedure must be recorded.
21	Technical/organizational measures to ensure acceptable use and safe handling of assets must be implemented.
22	Technical/organizational measures to ensure adequate commissioning and decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the PolicyCLOUD platform in the production environment must be implemented. These must include (in the case of decommissioning) measures to ensure the complete and permanent deletion of the data or the proper destruction of the media.
23	An asset classification schema that reflects for each asset the protection needs of the information it processes, stores, or transmits must be defined.
24	When applicable, all assets must be labelled according to their classification in the asset classification schema.
25	Security perimeters must be defined in the buildings and premises related to the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
26	At least two security areas must be defined, with one covering all buildings and premises and one covering sensitive activities such as the buildings and premises hosting the information system for the production of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
27	A set of security requirements for each security area must be defined and communicated.
28	Technical/organizational measures to ensure adequate physical access control to the security areas must be implemented, requiring at least one authentication factor for accessing any non-public area. Derogations in case of emergency must be defined.
29	A warning must be displayed at the entrance of all non-public perimeters concerning the limits and access conditions to these perimeters.
30	Security perimeters must be protected with security measures to detect and prevent unauthorised access in a timely manner so that it does not compromise the information security of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
31	Technical/organizational measures concerning the protection of equipment must be implemented, covering at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage;• Protecting equipment during maintenance operations;• Protecting equipment holding data during transport.

Control No.	Description
32	Encryption must be used on the removable media and the backup media intended to move between security areas according to the sensitivity of the data stored on the media.
33	A set of security requirements related to external and environmental threats must be documented and communicated, addressing the following risks in accordance with the applicable legal and contractual requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faults in planning; • Unauthorised access; • Insufficient surveillance; • Insufficient air-conditioning; • Fire and smoke; • Water; • Power failure; and • Air ventilation and filtration.
34	Technical/organizational measures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources) must be implemented, which shall include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload.
35	Requirements must be included in contractual agreements with PolicyCLOUD users (or their organisations) regarding the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform in case of capacity bottlenecks or personnel and IT resources outages.
36	Technical/organizational measures to ensure the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of the services linked to the PolicyCLOUD platform, to ensure compliance with the contractual agreements with PolicyCLOUD users (or their organisations), must be implemented.
37	PolicyCLOUD users must be able to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if these corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to those users.
38	Technical/organizational measures to protect PolicyCLOUD platform systems and users from malware must be implemented, covering at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of system-specific protection mechanisms; • Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the Consortium that are used to provide the PolicyCLOUD platform in the production environment; and • Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.
39	Malware protection must be deployed, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the PolicyCLOUD platform in the production environment.
40	Technical/organizational measures to ensure adequate data backup and recovery must be implemented.
41	Technical/organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups must be implemented.
42	Restore procedures must be tested.
43	Backup data must be transferred to a remote location or transported on backup media to a remote location.
44	Where backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data must take place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art.

Control No.	Description
45	Technical/organizational measures to ensure the logging and monitoring of events on system components must be implemented.
46	Technical/organizational measures to ensure the secure handling of derived data must be implemented.
47	Log data must be monitored in order to identify events that might lead to security incidents.
48	Identified events must be reported for timely assessment and remediation.
49	All log data must be stored in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation.
50	Log data must be deleted when it is no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected.
51	Communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers must be authenticated and protected in integrity and confidentiality.
52	Log data generated must allow an unambiguous identification of user accesses at the PolicyCLOUD user level to support analysis in the event of an incident.
53	Only authorized users may be allowed access to system components used for logging and monitoring under their responsibility.
54	The system components for logging and monitoring must be monitored, and failures must be automatically detected and reported.
55	Technical/organizational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the PolicyCLOUD platform must be implemented.
56	A scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities, that includes at least “critical” and “high” classes of vulnerabilities, must be implemented.
57	A publicly and easily accessible online register of known vulnerabilities that affect the PolicyCLOUD platform and assets provided which PolicyCLOUD users have to install or operate under their own responsibility must be published. This online register indicate at least the following information for every vulnerability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A presentation of the vulnerability following an industry-accepted scoring system; • A description of the remediation options for that vulnerability; • Information on the availability of updates or patches for that vulnerability; • Information about the remediation or deployment of patches or updates by the Consortium or the PolicyCLOUD user, including detailed instructions for operations to be performed by the user.
58	Tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the PolicyCLOUD platform must be carried out, ideally on a regular basis.
59	All the system components that are used to provide the PolicyCLOUD platform must be hardened, according to accepted industry standards.
60	PolicyCLOUD user data must be segregated, stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data.
61	Role and rights policies and procedures must be implemented for controlling access to information resources, in which at least the following aspects are covered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; • Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need-to-know” principle; • Use of a role-based mechanism for the assignment of access rights;

Control No.	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights; • Dedicated rules for users with privileged access; • Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights.
62	<p>Technical/organizational measures to ensure the adequate managing of accounts must be implemented, in which at least the following aspects are covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assignment of unique usernames; • Definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type; • Events leading to blocking and revoking accounts.
63	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate managing of personal user accounts and access rights to internal and external employees that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts.</p>
64	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate managing of non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts.</p>
65	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate managing of technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the PolicyCLOUD platform that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts.</p>
66	<p>An automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of time must be implemented.</p>
67	<p>An automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts must be implemented.</p>
68	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate granting, updating, and revoking to a user account of access rights to resources of the information system of the PolicyCLOUD platform, and these procedures shall be compliant with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing access rights.</p>
69	<p>Shared accounts under the responsibility of the Consortium shall be assigned only to internal or external employees.</p>
70	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate provisioning of authentication mechanisms, covering at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; • The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; • The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; • Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and • Rules on the required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules.
71	<p>All authentication mechanisms must include a mechanism to block an account after a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts.</p>
72	<p>Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate management of credentials, including at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-reuse of credentials;

Control No.	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize;• Recommendations for renewal of passwords;• Rules on storage of passwords.
73	Passwords must be only stored using cryptographically strong hash functions.
74	Sufficient partitioning measures between the information system providing the PolicyCLOUD platform and other information systems must be implemented.
75	Suitable measures for partitioning between PolicyCLOUD users must be implemented.
76	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate encryption and key management, in which at least the following aspects are covered: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols;• Requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys;• Consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements.
77	Strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of data over public networks must be implemented.
78	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate encryption of data during storage.
79	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate and secure key management, including at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications;• Issuing and obtaining public-key certificates;• Provisioning and activation of the keys;• Secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access;• Changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised;• Handling of compromised keys; and• Withdrawal and deletion of keys.
80	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure the adequate and prompt detection and response to network-based attacks and to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems.
81	Specific security requirements to connect within the PolicyCLOUD network must be implemented, defining at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• When the security zones are to be separated and when the PolicyCLOUD users are to be logically or physically segregated;• What communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case;• How the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level;• What internal, cross-location communication is permitted; and• What cross-network communication is allowed.
82	Trusted and untrusted networks must be distinguished, based on a risk assessment.
83	Trusted and untrusted networks must be separated into different security zones for internal and external network areas (and DMZ, if applicable).

Control No.	Description
84	Both physical and virtualized network environments must be designed and configured to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to defined security requirements.
85	Each network perimeter must be controlled by security gateways.
86	Separate networks must be defined and implemented for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles.
87	Networks for administration must be logically/physically separated from PolicyCLOUD users' networks.
88	Networks used to migrate or create virtual machines must be physically/logically segregated.
89	Segregation mechanisms at network level between the data traffic of different PolicyCLOUD users must be implemented.
90	Up-to-date all documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the PolicyCLOUD platform must be maintained. This documentation must cover, at least, how the subnets are allocated, how the network is zoned and segmented, how it connects with third-party and public networks, and the geographical locations in which data are stored.
91	The confidentiality of data must be ensured by suitable procedures when offering functions for software-defined networking (SDN).
92	The functionality of SDN functions must be validated before providing new SDN features to PolicyCLOUD users or modifying existing SDN features.
93	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction.
94	The PolicyCLOUD platform must only be accessible by cloud services from other providers or PolicyCLOUD users' IT systems through documented inbound and outbound interfaces.
95	The interfaces shall be clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data.
96	Communication on these interfaces shall use standardised communication protocols that ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted information according to its protection requirements.
97	Communication over untrusted networks shall be encrypted.
98	Contractual agreements applicable to PolicyCLOUD users (or their organisations) must include, at least, the following aspects concerning the termination of the contractual relationship: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Type, scope and format of the data the PolicyCLOUD platform provides to the user;• Delivery methods of the data to the user;• Definition of the timeframe, within which the Platform makes the data available to the user;• Definition of the point in time as of which the Platform makes the data inaccessible to the user and deletes the data; and• Responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data.
99	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented for deleting PolicyCLOUD users' data (including metadata and data stored in backups) upon termination of their contract in compliance with the relevant contractual agreements.

Control No.	Description
100	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate change management of the IT systems supporting the PolicyCLOUD platform. Changes must be categorized and prioritized considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned, and must be tested and approved before deployment.
101	Roles and rights must be defined for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the PolicyCLOUD platform in the production environment.
102	All changes to the PolicyCLOUD platform in the production environment shall be logged and shall be traceable back to the individual or system component that initiated the change.
103	Version control procedures must be implemented to track the dependencies of individual changes and to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities.
104	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate and secure development of the PolicyCLOUD platform, which must consider information security from the earliest phases of design.
105	A list of dependencies to hardware and software products used in the development of the PolicyCLOUD platform must be maintained.
106	The confidentiality and integrity of the source code must be adequately protected at all stages of development.
107	Version control must be used to keep a history of the changes in source code with an attribution of changes to individual developers.
108	Production environments must be physically or logically separated from development, test or pre-production environments.
109	Data contained in the production environments must not be used in development, test or preproduction environments in order not to compromise their confidentiality.
110	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate checking of the PolicyCLOUD platform for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the Platform during the development process.
111	The procedures for identifying vulnerabilities must be integrated in the development process.
112	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate controlling and monitoring of third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
113	A risk assessment of suppliers involved in the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform must be performed and, where relevant, complementary requirements must be identified and implemented by those suppliers.
114	A directory for controlling and monitoring the suppliers who contribute to the delivery of the PolicyCLOUD platform must be maintained.
115	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate analysis, evaluation and treatment of identified violations and deviations by suppliers.
116	When a change in a third-party contributing to the delivery of the PolicyCLOUD platform affects its level of security, technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure that all PolicyCLOUD users can be informed of this without delay.
117	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure a fast, effective and proper response to all known security incidents.

Control No.	Description
118	Analyses of security incidents must be performed to identify recurrent or significant incidents and to identify the need for further protection.
119	All documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents must be archived.
120	Security mechanisms and processes must be implemented for protecting all the information related to security incidents in accordance with criticality levels and legal requirements in effect.
121	Technical/organizational measures must be implemented to ensure adequate business continuity and contingency management, which must include the need to perform a business impact analysis to determine the impact of any malfunction to the PolicyCLOUD platform or its infrastructure.
122	The CSP shall document the legal, regulatory, self-imposed and contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the PolicyCLOUD platform.
123	Guidelines and recommendations to assist PolicyCLOUD users with the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the PolicyCLOUD platform must be made publicly available.
124	Guidelines and recommendations applicable to the PolicyCLOUD platform in the version intended for productive use must be maintained.
125	Comprehensible and transparent information must be provided to PolicyCLOUD users on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The relevant jurisdiction applicable to the provision of the PolicyCLOUD platform; and • System component locations, including its subcontractors, where data is processed, stored and backed up.
126	Sufficient information must be provided for PolicyCLOUD users' subject matter experts to determine to assess the suitability of the PolicyCLOUD platform's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective.
127	PolicyCLOUD users must be offered error handling and logging mechanisms that allow them to obtain security-related information about the security status of the PolicyCLOUD platform as well as the data, services or functions it provides.
128	A suitable session management system must be used that at least corresponds to the state-of-the-art and is protected against known attacks.
129	The following aspects must be ensured if PolicyCLOUD users operate virtual machines or containers with the PolicyCLOUD platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user can restrict the selection of images of virtual machines or containers according to their specifications, so that they can only launch the images or containers released according to these restrictions; • In addition, these images provided by the Platform are hardened according to generally accepted industry standards.

TABLE 7 – WP2 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

Annex 2 – Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist

Updated WP3 Legal/Ethical Checklist, as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	It is necessary to have a clear and specific framework in place with the IaaS provider, in which objectives, processes and results expected from PolicyCLOUD platform are clearly set out, so as to specify the capabilities needed from the IaaS provider.	Closed	A Service Level Agreement and Operational Level Agreement with the IaaS service providers have been entered into (EGI / ReCaS - Bari).
2	The framework developed with the IaaS provider must define appropriate service levels so as to ensure that the platform and its data will be kept promptly available to PolicyCLOUD and end-users, identifying a maximum amount of acceptable service downtime and ensuring the possibility to recover data which may be lost during the interruption. Infringement of these levels should preferably be subjected to appropriate contractual penalties.	Closed	A Service Level Agreement and Operational Level Agreement with the IaaS service providers have been entered into (EGI / ReCaS - Bari).
3	The environmental impact of the infrastructure necessary to support the functioning of the cloud-based system should be reduced to a minimum.	Ongoing	===
4	Adequate technical and organisational security measures must be implemented in the components developed by WP3, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis. Specific measures aimed at ensuring data integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data used as input, the functioning of the analytics components, or the output generated by those components) should be considered in this assessment, as well as specific measures aimed at ensuring data confidentiality/availability (where input	Ongoing	Matters related to security must be coordinated at the Project-level - relevant security standards are currently being identified, after which it should be possible for WP3 to define a viable approach to security (in line with the other WPs). In particular, once the approach to security has been defined (in terms of relevant

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	<p>datasets may be stored on the platform), and restrictions on reuse of personal data (e.g., hashing or encryption).</p> <p>The ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents, including personal data breaches, must also be considered.</p> <p>The technical and organisational security measures put in place by the IaaS provider in relation to the cloud infrastructure should sufficiently mitigate any relevant risks identified.</p>		<p>standards to be implemented/followed, it will be necessary to assess the security measures provided by the IaaS provider, to ensure alignment with the defined approach.</p> <p>This will primarily be done through the revision, consolidation and implementation of the WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist.</p>
5	<p>The Platform should be designed so as to facilitate the exercise of rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws to the relevant data subjects (i.e., platform users).</p> <p>This may include measures such as setting up a dedicated e-mail inbox to receive requests for the exercise of these rights, as well as an internal workflow which allows for adequate management of these requests within the timeframe provided by the GDPR (as a rule, requests must be addressed within one month from receipt).</p> <p>Furthermore, the Platform should be designed so as to not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights.</p>	Ongoing	<p>The abilities described in Table 3 of Section 2.2.4 of this Deliverable can be covered on the PolicyCLOUD platform, at least through manual intervention by system administrators.</p>
6	<p>Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.</p>	Ongoing	<p>A Data Governance and Privacy Enforcement mechanism has been developed for the PolicyCLOUD platform.</p>
7	<p>PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data (of platform users) in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.</p>	Ongoing	<p>A mechanism for deletion of PolicyCLOUD user data will be implemented.</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	<p>Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than actually needed, unless a reason for further processing exists, and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle.</p> <p>Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.</p>		
8	<p>A Data Processing Agreement (DPA) shall be executed between PolicyCLOUD and the IaaS provider, including all the requirements defined by Art. 28 GDPR.</p>	Ongoing	<p>EGI.eu has since made template data processing agreements available, which may be used to complement the OLA and SLA with additional obligations upon EGI.eu/the provider. In particular, the template DPA with EGI Foundation as a Processor relevant to Cloud Compute services [29] may, subject to a full assessment and consolidation of its contents to ensure its adequacy in light of the personal data processing activities relevant to the PolicyCLOUD project, be leveraged for these purposes.</p>

TABLE 8 – UPDATED WP3 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

Annex 3 – Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist

Updated WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist, as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	<p>The platform's analytic components (including analytic-ingest components) must be covered by an appropriate initial and routine training and testing protocol/program.</p> <p>This protocol/program must aim to mitigate the risk that the components may skew knowledge obtained from data (output) in a biased or otherwise erroneous manner. It must also aim to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for output generated (e.g., in the case of Enhanced Interoperability, for annotations and connections established).</p>	Ongoing	<p>The specific Consortium members responsible for each relevant tool will be engaged to provide information about the training and testing protocols/programs applicable (or to be applied, where relevant) to the tools for which they are responsible</p> <p>A requirement has been set for PolicyCLOUD users seeking to register a tool to document measures taken to address applicable legal/ethical requirements, through adequate fields added to the registration Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by tool registrants require them to link bias management information / documentation to the tool upon registration.</p>
2	<p>Adequate technical and organisational security measures must be implemented in the components developed by WP4, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated, in particular, from reliance on big data analysis.</p> <p>Specific measures aimed at ensuring data integrity (e.g., prevention of external attacks affecting the integrity of data used as input, the functioning of the</p>	Ongoing	<p>Matters related to security must be coordinated at the Project-level - relevant security standards are currently being identified, after which it should be possible for WP4 to define a viable approach to security (in line with the other WPs).</p> <p>This will primarily be done through the revision, consolidation and implementation of the WP2 Legal/Ethical Checklist.</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	<p>analytics components, or the output generated by those components) should be considered in this assessment, as well as specific measures aimed at ensuring data confidentiality/availability (where input datasets may be stored on the platform), and restrictions on reuse of personal data (e.g., hashing or encryption).</p> <p>The ability to detect and appropriately respond to security incidents, including personal data breaches, must also be considered.</p>		
3	<p>Mechanisms facilitating the auditability of AI systems (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data, and the logging of the AI system processes, outcomes, and positive and negative impacts) must be implemented.</p> <p>These logs should assist in ensuring traceability of automated decisions (i.e., explaining how an algorithm arrived at a given output from a given input), as well as the presentation of correlations established and their rationale to the end-user for confirmation. This information should allow end-users to validate correlations made to some extent.</p>	Ongoing	<p>A standard logging service has been implemented in the platform, as a centralised, PolicyCLOUD project-wide component (as reported in Section 2.3.2 of D4.3 [33]).</p> <p>The specific Consortium members responsible for each relevant tool will be engaged to provide information about the mechanisms facilitating auditability of AI-based systems (including the traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data used, the logging of processes/outcomes/impacts) applicable (or to be applied, where relevant) to the tools for which they are responsible.</p>
4	<p>Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.</p>		<p>The specific Consortium members responsible for each relevant tool will be engaged to provide information about the trade-offs between applicable legal/ethical requirements and principles considered during design applicable (or to be</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p>applied, where relevant) to the tools for which they are responsible.</p> <p>A requirement has been set for PolicyCLOUD users seeking to register a tool to document measures taken to address applicable legal/ethical requirements, through adequate fields added to the registration Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by tool registrants require them to link trade-off management information / documentation to the tool upon registration.</p>
5	Should the use of a selected data source be subject to restrictions (e.g., contractual terms, database copyright protection, database <i>sui generis</i> right protection, copyright protection), that data source should not be used without appropriate permissions from the relevant owners/rightsholders of that data source.	Ongoing	A requirement has been set for PolicyCLOUD users seeking to register a data source to document measures taken to address applicable legal requirements, through adequate fields added to the registration Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by tool registrants require them to link information / documentation to confirm and/or demonstrate that the registration of the data source has been authorised by relevant rightsholders (or that such authorisation is not required under the EU legal framework), to the data source upon registration.
6	The Platform should be designed so as to facilitate the exercise of rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws to	Ongoing	The PolicyCLOUD user is in control of the level of aggregation/anonymisation applied to cleaned/ingested data

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	<p>the relevant data subjects (i.e., individuals whose personal data may be stored within cleaned/ingested datasets).</p> <p>This may include measures such as setting up a dedicated e-mail inbox to receive requests for the exercise of these rights, as well as an internal workflow which allows for adequate management of these requests within the timeframe provided by the GDPR (as a rule, requests must be addressed within one month from receipt).</p> <p>Furthermore, the Platform should be designed so as to not create any relevant technical obstacles to the exercise of these rights. In particular, regarding personal data stored within cleaned/ingested datasets, it should be possible to manipulate those personal data as needed to respond to any of the requests described in the "Data Subject Rights" tab.</p>		<p>(i.e., the user will be able to determine whether any personal data is contained within datasets stored on the platform).</p> <p>Where personal data is stored, there should not be any relevant technical obstacle to carrying out further "cleaning" operations on cleaned/ingested data, as needed to address data subject rights requests in practice.</p>
7	Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.	Ongoing	A Data Governance and Privacy Enforcement mechanism has been developed for the PolicyCLOUD platform.
8	PolicyCLOUD shall only collect personal data, which is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. As such, for each purpose of processing connected to the Project, it shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.	Ongoing	The PolicyCLOUD user is in control of the specific data points which will be cleaned/ingested and stored on the platform - attribute/data point filtering is part of the cleaning process. When registering a data source, the user will be able to specify the attributes which are to be further processed as part of the data source's parameters. This

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p>will allow the user to configure the platform so that personal data is not unnecessarily collected - in other words, to either prevent or minimize the collection of personal data (e.g., by refraining from collecting relevant identifiers).</p> <p>Regarding the specific data sources to be used in the context of the Project, the specific attributes which are to be further processed are under validation from the legal perspective (work developed in WP6 – see WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklists). Once these have been defined, the resulting groups of attributes should be further assessed to confirm whether anonymisation, under the GDPR, has been effectively achieved.</p> <p>A requirement has been set for PolicyCLOUD users seeking to register a data source to document measures taken to address applicable legal requirements, through adequate fields added to the registration Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). In particular, specific parameters to be addressed by tool registrants require them to link privacy / data protection management information / documentation to the data source upon registration.</p>
9	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, and to	Ongoing	The transformation and “pre-processing” of data (as better described in <u>Sections 3.2.1.2 and</u>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	maintain those personal data up to date over time.		<p>3.2.2 of D4.3 [33]), include activities such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data validation, to ensure that the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform components operates on clean, correct and useful data. This also involves assessing the data against defined constraints (which may be mandatory or optional), as a way to provide further assurances as to the accuracy and consistency of data processed via the platform; • Data cleaning, to correct or remove all data for which validation errors were raised during the validation process, including missing, irregular, unnecessary and inconsistent data. This also involves deleting or replacing data which is not aligned with the defined constraints; • Data verification, to check the data for accuracy and any remaining inconsistencies, after the validation and cleaning processes have been completed. <p>Mandatory and optional data constraints can be defined to configure the parameters under</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			which these data validation, cleaning and verification activities operate. This should afford control to PolicyCLOUD users over the specific data points of a data source to be registered and leveraged via the PolicyCLOUD platform. This will allow users to configure the platform so that personal data is not unnecessarily collected or processed, thereby allowing unnecessary personal data to be removed from data sources prior to their further storage and processing via the PolicyCLOUD platform. Furthermore, various libraries are exploited in connection with the platform's data validation, cleaning and verification activities to provide greater assurances of data quality (including accuracy, completeness and lack of errors).
10	End-users should also be advised of the possibility of false positive/negative correlations, so that they are incentivised to verify the validity of correlations made.	Ongoing	The specific Consortium members responsible for each relevant tool will be engaged to provide information about the degree of possibility of false positive/negative correlations, applicable (or to be applied, where relevant) to the tools for which they are responsible.

TABLE 9 – UPDATED WP4 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

Annex 4 – Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist

Updated WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist, as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	===
2	The platform should incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats generated from reliance on big data analysis.	Ongoing	===
3	PolicyCLOUD must assess which of the legal bases afforded by the GDPR may be applicable and implementable for an intended processing of personal data. This assessment must consider the full context of the processing activities which are intended, including the specific data sources to be used and the specific goals to be reached using the platform.	Closed	<p>An appropriate legal basis for each purpose for which personal data on PolicyCLOUD users may be collected has been identified, under Art. 6 GDPR. All steps needed to properly implement the identified legal bases have been taken, depending on the legal bases selected, which in turn depends on the way user personal are processed via the PDT. The legal bases identified to this regard are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compliance with legal requirements, according with Art. 6, par. 1, let. c) GDPR. 2. The legitimate interest of both PolicyCLOUD and the organization of which the end user is

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p>part to the proper operation of the platform, according with Art. 6, par. 1, let. f) GDPR.</p> <p>3. The legitimate interest of PolicyCLOUD and the organization using the platform to protect the platform and the information included in the same platform, according with Art. 6, par. 1, let. f) GDPR.</p> <p>4. The establishment, exercise, or defense of legal claims, according with Art. 6, par. 1, let. f) GDPR.</p>
4	PolicyCLOUD should only handle personal data in ways that may be reasonably expected and not use such data in a way that may produce unjustified adverse effects on data subjects.	Ongoing	===
5	When data subjects seek to exercise their rights granted by the GDPR or other applicable data protection laws PolicyCLOUD shall be capable to facilitate the exercise of these rights.	Closed	<p>Mechanisms are in place to ensure that users can exercise their rights in relation to any personal data of theirs which may be collected during the use of the platform. More specifically, each data subject can exercise the following rights by sending a request in writing to PolicyCLOUD, to the extent permitted by applicable law:</p> <p>1. To access. The data subject can obtain information relating to the processing of their personal data and a copy of such personal data.</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<ol style="list-style-type: none">2. To erase. The data subject can require the deletion of their personal data, to the extent permitted by law.3. To object. The data subject can object to the processing of their personal data, on grounds relating to their situation. In cases of opposition to the processing of personal data, PolicyCLOUD reserves the right to assess the request, which will not be accepted if there are legitimate reasons to proceed with the processing that prevail over the freedoms, interests, and rights of the data subject.4. To rectify. Where the data subject consider that their personal data is inaccurate or incomplete, they can require that such personal data be modified accordingly.5. To restrict. The data subject can request the restriction of the processing of their personal data. <p>Furthermore, should the data subject believe that the processing of their personal data is contrary to the legislation in force, they have the right to lodge a complaint to the competent data</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			protection supervisory authority.
6	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Closed	A specific privacy policy has been developed for the PDT, to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the PDT in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR.
7	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Closed	A specific privacy policy has been developed for the PDT, to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the PDT in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR.
8	PolicyCLOUD shall made available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Closed	The data protection information notice is provided to the end users of the platform using a two-layer approach: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first layer is represented by a pop-up banner which appears to the end user when visiting the platform. This pop-up banner includes a link to the second layer data protection information notice (i.e., the extended version of the data protection information notice). 2. The second layer is represented by the extended version of the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			data protection information notice, including all the elements required by Arts 13 and 14 GDPR. This extended version of the data protection information notice, the text of which is provided under D8.1. [3], is accessible to end users by clicking on a footer named “End Users Data Protection Information Notice” published on all the pages of the web environment on which the platform operates.
9	Platform users shall be limited both from a technical and from a contractual point of view in how they can process personal data which are collected and managed through the PolicyCLOUD platform.	Ongoing	===
10	Internal policies shall be implemented to make users aware of what they can and cannot do with the personal data collected for the different use cases and more in general for the execution of the Project.	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD should implement technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.	Ongoing	===
12	PolicyCLOUD shall only collect personal data, which is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. As such, for each purpose of processing connected to the Project, it shall	Closed	Only the strict minimum amount of user personal data needed for the above listed purposes are collected. More specifically, the personal data of the end users of the platform

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.		processed by PolicyCLOUD are the following: 1. Name. 2. E-mail address. 3. Organization and role. 4. Username and password. 5. IP address. 6. Event logs related to the use of the platform.
13	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Closed	Users are given the possibility to rectify any personal data they submit, or which is collected on them, in connection with use of the PDT, by sending a request in writing to PolicyCLOUD.
14	PolicyCLOUD shall implement technical and organisational measures aimed at guaranteeing the accuracy and quality of personal data included in the cloud-based platform and shall provide means to data subjects for contributing to the maintenance of data that is always accurate and up to date.	Ongoing	===
15	PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than needed, unless a reason for further processing exists, and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle. Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.		
16	It should be demonstrable that the security measures implemented on the platform were chosen as a result of a documented risk assessment, with justifications as to why those measures were deemed adequate to address the specific risks identified.	Ongoing	===
17	There should be clearly defined rules and specific channels on the reporting of security incidents or abnormal events related to the platform., and all persons working with the platform should be made aware of the types of occurrences which may qualify as a reportable security incident.	Ongoing	===
18	The processes implemented to address personal data breaches by PolicyCLOUD should ensure that all relevant information on a personal data breach and the manner in which it was handled is documented in a register of personal data breaches, as set out in Art. 33, par. 5 GDPR, including all facts pertaining to the personal data breach, its effects and remedial action taken, including notifications to end-users, supervisory authorities and/or data subjects, as well as all technical and organizational mitigation measures applied, documented assessments carried out, including those performed to classify the incident as a personal data breach, as well as to classify a personal data breach in terms of category and severity level. Post-breach analyses should also be carried out, to validate the effectiveness of the breach management process, identify areas	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	of improvement, and identify, based on a root cause analysis of the incident, adequate technical and organisational measures to reduce or eliminate the likelihood of recurrence.		
19	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
20	A security risk assessment, as part of an overall DPIA, should be carried out, to identify possible threats and risks to the fundamental rights, freedoms and interests of Data Subjects and the specific security measures implemented or which should be implemented to address them.	Ongoing	===
21	It should be defined terms and conditions for the use of the PDT, to properly regulate the service relationship established between PolicyCLOUD and the end-user or the organisation to which the end-user belongs. These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for the use of the PDT to be allowed.	Ongoing	===
22	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 10 – UPDATED WP5 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST

Annex 5 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

1: Scenario A (Radicalization Incidents)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario A (Radicalization Incidents), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.		
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).		dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	public websites under their control.		data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
14	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario A (Radicalization incidents) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).

TABLE 11 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 1: SCENARIO A (RADICALIZATION INCIDENTS)

Annex 6 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

1: Scenario B (Radicalized Groups and Individuals)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario B (Radicalized Groups and Individuals), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).		and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g.,

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
14	All relevant GDPR and EU Directive 2016/680 principles (e.g., lawfulness,	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) shall be covered.		and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).
15	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Closed / Not Applicable	In the context of UC #1, scenario B (Radicalized groups and individuals) does not raise specific concerns with regards to personal data compliance. Indeed, for this scenario the relevant data sources identified in D1.3 [5] are dataset 7 (GTD) [6] and dataset 8 (RDWTI) [7], which include non-personal data and/or personal data of public domain (e.g., information regarding well known terrorists, victims of terrorist attacks, and/or any other person involved in terroristic events).

TABLE 12 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 1: SCENARIO B (RADICALIZED GROUPS AND INDIVIDUALS)

Annex 7 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

1: Scenario C (Trend Analysis)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario C (Trend Analysis), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).		
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	===
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	===
14	All relevant GDPR and EU Directive 2016/680 principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) shall be covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The requirements of the EDPB Guidelines 08/2020 on the targeting of social media users (considering the databases to be used) shall be respected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===

TABLE 13 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 1: SCENARIO C (TREND ANALYSIS)

Annex 8 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

1: Scenario D ([Near] Real-time Assessment of Online Propaganda)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 1: Scenario D ([Near] Real-time Assessment of Online Propaganda), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	===
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	===
14	All relevant GDPR and EU Directive 2016/680 principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation) shall be covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The requirements of the EDPB Guidelines 08/2020 on the targeting of social media users (considering the databases to be used) shall be respected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted (to be balanced with EU Directive 2016/680).	Ongoing	===

TABLE 14 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 1: SCENARIO D ([NEAR] REAL-TIME ASSESSMENT OF ONLINE PROPAGANDA)

Annex 9 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

2: Scenario A (Price of Wine)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario A (Price of Wine), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	===
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.		
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	===
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	===
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	===
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The requirements of the EDPB Guidelines 08/2020 on the targeting of social media users (considering the databases to be used) shall be respected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 15 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 2: SCENARIO A (PRICE OF WINE)

Annex 10 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

2: Scenario B (Opinions on Social Networks)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario B (Opinions on Social Networks), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.	Ongoing	===
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	===
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	===
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	===
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The requirements of the EDPB Guidelines 08/2020 on the targeting of social media users (considering the databases to be used) shall be respected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 16 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 2: SCENARIO B (OPINIONS ON SOCIAL NETWORKS)

Annex 11 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

2: Scenario C (Trend Analysis)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 2: Scenario C (Trend Analysis), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Ongoing	===
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Ongoing	===
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	===

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.	Ongoing	===
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	===
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	===
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	===
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	===
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The requirements of the EDPB Guidelines 08/2020 on the targeting of social media users (considering the databases to be used) shall be respected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 17 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 2: SCENARIO C (TREND ANALYSIS)

Annex 12 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 1 (Road Infrastructure)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 1 (Road Infrastructure), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research,</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 18 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 1 (ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE)

Annex 13 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 2 (Environment and Air Quality)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 2 (Environment and Air Quality), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p>are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user. Furthermore, from a contractual standpoint, the end-user is generally authorized to use Airthings data as intended by the UC, since the terms made available by Airthings online (Section 4 of the Specific Terms for Subscription Services) state that <i>"Airthings grants the Customer a limited, nonexclusive, non-sublicensable, non-transferable license under intellectual property rights to use the Airthings application programming interface ("Airthings API") for the purpose of developing and implementing customer specific software solutions, products and applications integrating with products and services". [15]</i></p>
5	<p>Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.</p>	<p>Closed / Not applicable</p>	<p>Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user. Furthermore, from a contractual standpoint, the</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p>end-user is generally authorized to use Airthings data as intended by the UC, since the terms made available by Airthings online (Section 4 of the Specific Terms for Subscription Services) state that <i>"Airthings grants the Customer a limited, nonexclusive, non-sublicensable, non-transferable license under intellectual property rights to use the Airthings application programming interface ("Airthings API") for the purpose of developing and implementing customer specific software solutions, products and applications integrating with products and services"</i>. [15]</p>
6	<p>Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.</p>	<p>Closed / Not applicable</p>	<p>Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user. Furthermore, from a contractual standpoint, the end-user is generally authorized to use Airthings data as intended by the UC, since the terms made available by Airthings online</p>

Control No.	Recommendation / activities concerned / explanation	Examples of / further	Implementation Status	Notes
				(Section 4 of the Specific Terms for Subscription Services) state that <i>"Airthings grants the Customer a limited, nonexclusive, non-sublicensable, non-transferable license under intellectual property rights to use the Airthings application programming interface ("Airthings API") for the purpose of developing and implementing customer specific software solutions, products and applications integrating with products and services"</i> . [15]
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.		Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities		Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	<p>performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.</p>		<p>to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i></p>
9	<p>PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.</p>	Ongoing	<p>With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling,</i></p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: " <i>The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.		suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 19 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 2 (ENVIRONMENT AND AIR QUALITY)

Annex 14 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 3 (Waste Collection and Waste Disposal)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 3 (Waste Collection and Waste Disposal), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	authorization from the data source owner.		contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the UC.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to data subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further

Control No.	Recommendation / activities concerned / explanation	Examples of / further	Implementation Status	Notes
				processed in the context of UC #3 [3].

TABLE 20 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 3 (WASTE COLLECTION AND WASTE DISPOSAL)

Annex 15 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 4 (Transport and Parking)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 4 (Transport and Parking), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research,</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].

TABLE 21 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 4 (TRANSPORT AND PARKING)

Annex 16 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 5 (Cleanliness of Public Spaces)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 5 (Cleanliness of Public Spaces), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3. [3]
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].

TABLE 22 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 5 (CLEANLINESS OF PUBLIC SPACES)

Annex 17 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

3: Scenario 6 (Violation of Public Order)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 3: Scenario 6 (Violation of Public Order), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Sofia Municipality) is also responsible for the management of the contact center, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based	Ongoing	With regards to the data protection information notice

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.		published on the Sofia Municipality website [23], it would be appropriate to integrate it with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to Sofia Municipality may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i> .
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Ongoing	Dataset 18 [5] is intended to be purged of identifiers concerning the citizens submitting signals before its processing via PolicyCLOUD. However, this dataset currently includes information on the content provided by citizens within free text fields in each signal, which may reveal further personal data on the submitting citizens. To this regard, the corresponding UC partner has noted that no text analysis is intended to be performed on these fields, such that any such personal data will not be further processed in the context of UC #3 [3].

TABLE 23 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 3: SCENARIO 6 (VIOLATION OF PUBLIC ORDER)

Annex 18 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

4: Scenario A (Citizens Affected by Unemployment)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario A (Citizens Affected by Unemployment), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
	authorization from the data source owner.		contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Closed / Not applicable	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p><i>Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i></p>
10	<p>PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.</p>	Ongoing	<p>To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of</i></p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].

TABLE 24 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 4: SCENARIO A (CITIZENS AFFECTED BY UNEMPLOYMENT)

Annex 19 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

4: Scenario B (Predictive Analysis)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario B (Predictive Analysis), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Closed / Not applicable	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
10	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].

TABLE 25 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 4: SCENARIO B (PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS)

Annex 20 – Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC

4: Scenario C (Trends Analysis)

Updated WP6 Legal/Ethical Checklist – UC # 4: Scenario C (Trends Analysis), as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users shall take responsibility for what is done with personal data and how it complies with the personal data protection principles, implementing measures, documents, and records to demonstrate that appropriate processes and procedures are in place to ensure that personal data are collected, processed, and stored in such a way that is compliant with the GDPR and with other applicable data protection laws.	Ongoing	===
2	Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.	Ongoing	===
3	Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.	Ongoing	===
4	Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the data source owner.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
5	Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
6	Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorization from the rights holder.	Closed / Not applicable	Since the end-user (i.e., Camden Council) is also responsible for the management of this database, there are no contractual restrictions towards leveraging information obtained via the contact center for the purposes of the end-user. For the same reason, there are no IP law limitations related to the use of the data source by the end-user.
7	End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.	Closed / Not applicable	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
8	The platform and its end-users must weigh the interests of the data subjects appropriately and find effective means to provide information about the activities performed on personal data, also considering the need to preserve the quality of information in cases where providing this information may have an impact on the effectiveness of the use case.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
9	PolicyCLOUD and the end-users must be clear and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or</i>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<p><i>aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i></p>
10	<p>PolicyCLOUD and the end-users, in relation to the processing activities which they may respectively perform, as controllers, shall lay down a specific and easily accessible document which duly informs data subjects of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project: a privacy policy.</p>	Ongoing	<p>To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried</i></p>

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			<i>out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
11	PolicyCLOUD shall make available the privacy policy on its cloud-based platform, with appropriate steps taken to make it available to the data subjects whose personal data are used in the context of the Project. End-users should likewise ensure that the above information is available to Data Subjects on public websites under their control.	Ongoing	To comply with the transparency principle set forth by the GDPR, the general information notice provided to the citizens to which the data included in the Open Data Camden platform refer shall be integrated with the script suggested in D8.1 [3]: <i>"The personal data provided to the Camden Council may be, after anonymization and/or aggregation, used for research, analytical, statistical, and policymaking purposes. More specifically, the data may be used for the development of public policies, through the entire lifecycle of policy management (therefore including policy modelling, monitoring, enforcing, simulation, analysis, and compliance). The legal basis of the processing is the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, according with Art. 6(1)(e) GDPR."</i>
12	End-users shall be enabled to understand the output presented to them by the PDT.	Ongoing	===
13	Effective anonymization and/or aggregation methods shall be implemented.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
			does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].
14	All relevant GDPR principles (e.g., lawfulness, legal basis, purpose limitation, etc.) are covered.	Ongoing	===
15	The end-user should identify steps to reasonably assure itself of the reliability of the data source, in terms of the likelihood that any data collected from the data source may be false, inadequate, inaccurate, or incomplete, considering the purpose for which the data source is to be used. The end-user should identify, and document specific steps taken to address reliability and accuracy concerns detected.	Ongoing	===
16	The processing of minor data should be subjected to effective anonymization methods whenever feasible, even where individuals are targeted.	Closed	According to the information made available by the relevant UC partner, dataset 20 (Unemployment Claimant Count) does not contain any personal data, as defined under the GDPR, given that it does not contain any information attributable to identified or identifiable individuals (rather, the information therein is aggregated, statistical data about the population and other characteristics of the Camden borough in London) [3].

TABLE 26 – UPDATED WP6 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST – UC # 4: SCENARIO C (TRENDS ANALYSIS)

Annex 21 – WP7 Legal/Ethical Checklist

WP7 Legal/Ethical Checklist, as of the date of this Deliverable:

Control No.	Recommendation / Examples of activities concerned / further explanation	Implementation Status	Notes
1	The data marketplace should incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats.	Ongoing	===
2	Should non aggregated and/or anonymized personal data made available through the data marketplace, an appropriate legal basis to do so shall be identified, according with the GDPR.	Ongoing	===
3	PolicyCLOUD should be clear and honest with both the data subjects whose data are exchanged through the data marketplace and the clients of the data marketplace about the identity of the data controller which is collecting, processing, and storing personal data, the methods used to process personal data, and the purposes of processing.	Ongoing	===
4	It should be defined terms and conditions for the use of the data marketplace, to properly regulate the service relationship established between PolicyCLOUD and the end-user or the organisation to which the end-user belongs. These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for the participation to the data marketplace to be allowed.	Ongoing	===
5	A due diligence shall be performed, and a compliance declaration shall be obtained with regards to the ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal compliance of the datasets eventually uploaded to the data marketplace.	Ongoing	===

TABLE 27 – WP7 LEGAL/ETHICAL CHECKLIST